

The Role of the Entu Priestess in the Rise of Patriarch, Prophet and King

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Abstract

A striking feature of the Hebrew scriptures is the recurring figure of a foreign woman who brings forth the chosen child. She corresponds to the Mesopotamian *entu*—the high priestess of the moon god and daughter of the *šarru kiššati* (*King of All*). The *entu* mediated the divine kingship. Her literary provenance can be traced through the birth story of Moses, which retells the Birth Legend of Sargon. A comparison of the scribal acts of naming reveals an intricate interplay between Hebrew words and cuneiform ideographic concepts in the composite text. The scribe's command of this Akkadian source reveals sophisticated cuneiform skills, connecting the composition to the Babylonian exile and the 6th century Harranian ascendancy of the lunar deity Sîn. By repeatedly spiriting the *entu* away from the moon god cult, the scribes ritually transferred the divine kingship from Babylon (in various allegorical guises) to the shepherd clan. However, the presence of an indigenous high priestess in ancient Jerusalem can be pieced together from the available information. Through her, David gained the throne. The biblical account blends history with Mesopotamian scribal magic to secure the kingship of all (*šarrut kiššatim*) for the Davidic shepherd clan and the tribe of Judah.

Keywords

Akkadian, Allegory, Astarte, Divine Kingship, Ennigaldi, Goddess of Jerusalem, , Nabonidus, Pharaoh's Daughter, Scribal Magic

1. Introduction

According to the Birth Legend of Sargon, the future king's mother was an *entu*. This designation has been variously identified as princess, high priestess, vestal virgin, lowly woman and changeling.¹ It is evident from the diversity of translations that considerable confusion exists as to the role of the *entu* in general and to the narrative purpose of Sargon's *entu* mother in particular. This uncertainty is understandable in the case of translations made in the early stages of cuneiform discovery and

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¹ Carroll, *Moses' Name*, p. 776. In cuneiform texts, *entu* is written syllabically or with the logogram NIN.DINGIR.RA.

decipherment. However, the extensive archaeological and textual record available to us today removes the veil from the *entu*.

In Sumer and Akkad, this high cultic office was filled by a DUMU.SAL LUGAL—a royal daughter.² Penelope Weadock cites 15 historical *entu* priestesses in the cult of the moon god Nanna (Akk. *Sîn*).³ Each was the daughter of the preeminent monarch of the era. In the regnal terminology of the Mesopotamian empires, the father of the *entu* was the holder of the title *šarru kiššati*—King of All the Lands. When we apply this understanding to the Birth Legend of Sargon, it signals that Sargon’s mother was the daughter of Ur-Zababa of Kiš, who reigned over Sumer at that time. It is a critical point that has been missed in analyses of Sargon’s birth legend.

The reign of Sargon the Great (c. 2300 BC) pre-dates the era of Moses in the biblical timeline (c. 1300 BC) by a thousand years. The Sumerian Legend of Sargon (c. 1800 BC, Old Babylonian era) describes his divinely-aided rise to power but lacks his birth story.⁴ The later Akkadian Birth Legend of Sargon briefly recapitulates Sargon’s reign, with much of the tablet devoted to the narrative of the future king placed in the river as an infant.⁵ The oldest known birth legend manuscripts are Neo-Assyrian—discovered in the library of Ashurbanipal in Nineveh.

Although the Neo-Assyrian texts postdate the era of Moses in the biblical timeline, the oldest known Hebrew manuscript recording his birth story is a Dead Sea scroll dating from the Hasmonean era (mid to late second century BC), written in the post-exilic Aramaic script.⁶ The difference in age between the oldest Sargonic and oldest Mosaic birth texts is approximately 500 years (7th vs. 2nd centuries BC). Although both birth stories are assumed to be older than their surviving manuscripts, we do not possess hard evidence for this.⁷

The commonalities of the infant hero hidden in a sealed reed basket, consigned to the river and rescued by the substitute parent cannot be coincidental.¹ Given the existence of a substantially older text in the literary repertoire of the Mesopotamians who conquered the Fertile Crescent, the *a priori* probability is that the Birth Legend of Sargon inspired its Mosaic counterpart. Nevertheless, the scholarly literature predominantly views the two stories as semi-autonomous exemplars of the foundling child myth.⁵ This impression of generic cultural diffusion is strongly refuted by the specific and critical role played by the *entu* princess-priestess mothers of the two protagonists.

² The language references drawn upon are the *CAD*, *CDA*, *ePSD*, *SL*, *CSL* and *Sefaria DDB*.

³ Weadock, *Giparu at Ur*. The author states that the office of the *entu* at Ur likely dates back to the Early Dynastic period (c. 2900-2350 BCE).

⁴ Cooper and Heimpel, *Sumerian Sargon*.

⁵ Lewis, *Sargon Legend*.

⁶ 4Q1, dated by epigraphy (see Tigchelaar, *4Q1*). 4Q11 (written in the Old Hebrew script) has been variously dated between the 3rd and 1st centuries BCE (Dayfani, *4Q11*), but only retains two words from the birth story.

⁷ Hallo suggests that the Akkadian work was composed in the late 8th century BC “to celebrate the triumphs of his namesake, Sargon II” (*Book of the People*, p. 48).

Moses' adoptive mother was the “*daughter of Pharaoh*”. Moses' birth mother was from the priestly tribe of Levi (Exod 2:1).⁸ Although the Exodus account does not explicitly identify his birth mother as a priestess, the wording of her introduction to the narrative specifies that a man “*from the House of Levi*” took “*the daughter of Levi*”. The Hebrew phrasing links these two alliterative and poetically parallel clauses (*bt lwy/byt lwy*) to form a wordplay signaling that the Levite consorted with a votary of his sacral order. When considered from the Mesopotamian cultural perspective of the source account, she was a priestess (*bat bayīt—daughter of the temple*).⁹ Together they formed a conjugal pair.¹⁰ This sacred union produced not only Moses, but also Miriam the prophetess and Aaron—the founding archetype of the ideal priestly dynasty.¹¹

The mothers of Sargon and Moses thus share a sacerdotal context and a royal context. However, the Hebraic version divides this role between two women. Moses' birth mother and his adoptive mother are mirror images of each other—representing two faces of the *entu*. Why split the office between two women? If we assume that Moses was a well-known folk hero, he could not suddenly be transformed into the biological son of a foreign priestess from a Mesopotamian story. Likewise, if Moses was completely unknown before this story was written, he could hardly be presented as a Hebrew hero if he was the biological son of Pharaoh's daughter. In either case, the splitting of the *entu* role provides a narrative mechanism for drawing Moses forth from the classic Mesopotamian tale.

Moses' emergence as the towering figure of Judaism is a historical conundrum. No written attestation of the Old Hebrew equivalent of his name (*ꜥꜣꜣ*) has been recovered from archaeological excavations of ancient sites in Israel, Egypt or the intervening desert region. Moreover, no pre-exilic Hebrew scriptures have been found.¹² According to Yonatan Adler, the public observance of the Mosaic Law is not clearly detectable in the archaeological record until at least the Hellenistic Period (after 330 BC).¹³ If ordinary Judeans knew of Moses, they did not have a sense of the binding nature

⁸ The Hebrew scriptures conspicuously lack a general term for “*priestess*”—which surely existed in antiquity.

⁹ In Akkadian, priestesses could be referred to as *mārat bīti*, which is Heb. *bat bayīt*.

¹⁰ See Jacobsen, *Early Political Development*, pp. 107-108. In city states headed by a female deity (such as Uruk), the chosen priestess consorted with the *en* priest, who in ancient Sumer was also the ruler.

¹¹ Since Moses was her third child with Amram, the rabbis interpreted Exod 2:1 to mean that he formally married Jochebed again in preparation for Moses' conception (Baba Batra 119b:13, Sotah 12a:14). The missing (and rabbinically impermissible) concept of the *hieros gamos* (sacred marriage) may account for the appearance of “taking” a woman of Levi for the third time.

¹² The sole archaeological find of a pre-conquest scriptural analog are the Ketef Hinom amulets (c. 600 BC) discovered in a burial cave outside Jerusalem. Although they contain phrases found in the Priestly Benediction (Num 6:24-26), the context-of-use is independent of a temple setting. The words are integrated with other formulas designed to ward off evil. The texts do not cite Moses or the priests (see Barkay et al. *Ketef Hinnom*).

¹³ Adler notes that Sabbath prohibitions, fasting on Yom Kippur and the depiction of the seven-branched menorah first appear under Hasmonean rule.

of the Mosaic commandments until very late. Thus, from a strictly material viewpoint, we cannot assume Moses' antiquity. This raises the possibility that the birth story of Moses indeed marks his debut as a Hebrew folk-hero.

2. The Hidden Entu of the Hebrew Scriptures

Pharaoh's daughter in Moses' birth story is just one of many recurring appearances of an *entu* figure at key points in the biblical narrative. The matriarch Sarah (שרה—*princess*) was from Ur, the ancient epicenter of the Sumerian moon god cult. The office of the *entu* attained its greatest prominence in this Mesopotamian city-state. The Genesis narrative makes it clear that Abraham's sons by his other wives and concubines were not divinely chosen. As we shall see, this is a dynastic hallmark of the *entu*. In Hebraic form, the true heir of the lineage of Shem the shepherd could only be borne by Sarah. Likewise, Isaac's wife Rebecca was from Harran, the other Mesopotamian center of moon worship. She was the *daughter of Bethuel* (*bat b'ê tû 'ēl*), which may be understood literally as *daughter of the temple* (Heb. *bêt-ēl*, Akk. *bītu ilu*).¹⁴

In the third generation of matriarchs, Jacob's wives were daughters of Laban (*white*), an epithet of the moon (Heb. *l̄bānâ*). In the Harranian cultural context, the name Laban must be considered a cultic referent.¹⁵ When Jacob saw Rachel for the first time, he rolled away the enormous round stone (i.e. the *moon*) blocking the well of Harran, then “watered” (*yaš'q*) Laban's flock and “kissed” (*yīšaq*) Rachel (Gen 29:10-11). Akkadian *našāqu* means *to kiss, be bodily entwined*. The pun underscores the fertility symbolism inherent in Jacob's actions. This sequence foreshadows Jacob's theft of the *entu* from the cult of the moon god—and by extension his appropriation of the prosperity and glory of Harran (see Gen 31:1-31). The fact that the Genesis narrative repeats this acquisition in three consecutive generations underscores its importance.

In each generation, the king attempted to repossess his *entu* daughter. Abi-melech (*My father is king*;) tried to take Sarah from Abraham and Rebecca from Isaac. His city name Gerrar (גרר) is a cognate of Akkadian *gerru* (*road* or *way*), which is the meaning of Harran (*ḥarrānu*). Both *gerru* and *ḥarrānu* are written with the sign KASKAL (Sum. *road*). Both cities may be represented with the logogram KASKAL^{ki}. It appears that the Judean scribe chose this historical location as the setting for the contest over the *entu* based on its linguistic link to Harran.¹⁶ In another iteration,

¹⁴ The theophoric element ^dE₂.DINGIR (Akk. *bītu ilu*) is attested in 5th century Nippur (Hillprecht and Clay, *BE 9*, pl. 75). In the narrative setting of Harran, the name Bethuel implicitly refers to the famed E₂.ḪUL₂.ḪUL₂—the temple of Sîn.

¹⁵ Lewy notes the lunar theophoric element *la-ba-an* in Old Assyrian and Amorite personal names, citing Labanâ-ilâ as an example (*Hammu*, p. 434).

¹⁶ In addition, the homophone *gerû* means *enemy*, while ^{tu}g^{gar}arû designates the cloth covering the bed of the goddess in her temple upon which the *hieros gamos* took place.

Laban of Harran pursued Jacob to take back his daughters. As with Abimelech, Laban conceded his loss of the *entu* by concluding a treaty with the shepherd clan.

The biblical *entu* is also intrinsically connected to the monarchy of Israel. The royal line of Judah was conceived by Tamar while she acted in the role of a *q^e dēšāh*—a fertility priestess (Gen 38:12-30). Before consorting with Judah, Tamar asked for his (royal) staff and signet. Her impregnation took place in Timnah, which corresponds linguistically to Akkadian *timmēnu*—signifying *foundation* (often with a temple connotation). In a narrative parallel, Ruth the Moabitess (a descendant of Lot of Harran and his *entu* daughter) founded the House of David. She conceived David’s royal antecessor upon the grain heap of Bethlehem at harvest time (Ruth 3:6-9), underscoring the fertility motif of this *hieros gamos* (*sacred pairing*). The grain heap was located in the *gōren* (גרן), designating both a *threshing floor* and a *shrine*.¹⁷ The narrator (voiced through the elders sitting in the gateway of Bethlehem) directly ties the role of Ruth to that of Tamar (Ruth 4:12).

In terms of ritual context, the *hieros gamos* of the É-anna temple of Uruk took place in a ceremonial storeroom (*giparu*) containing harvested barley and dates.¹⁰ The union was between the high priest representing the shepherd Dumuzi (Tammuz) and the priestess representing Inanna (Ištar). Rūtu (*woman friend*) is an Akkadian epithet of Ištar. This background illuminates the scene of Ruth’s conception of the royal house of David (the shepherd) upon the barley heap of Bethlehem (בית־לחם)—the “*House of Grain*” (Ruth 3:6-9).¹⁷

In the generational timeline of pre-monarchic Israel, the entuship of Ruth follows that of Rahab of Jericho. The root *yrh* (ירח) in the city name *Yrhw* (ירחו) designates both the moon and the Canaanite lunar deity, *Yariḥ/Yarēah*.¹⁸ In the account of the destruction of this city, Joshua son of Nun sent two spies who were princes (see Num 13:2) to the house of Rahab, a symbol of Babylon (see Psa 87:14). She hid them on the roof (Jos 2:1-6), symbolically corresponding to the cuneiform sign UR₃. It depicts a house (GA₂) containing two princes (NUN/NUN). The Akkadian word *ganūnu* refers to the storeroom of a temple.

Rahab is called a *zônāh*, equivalent to a *q^e dēšāh* (see Gen 38:15, 21).¹⁹ According to the Talmud, Joshua married Rahab, whom the rabbis considered one of the most beautiful and intensely desirable women in history (Megillah 14b:13-15a). A pre-Talmudic tradition preserved in the

¹⁷ See Num 15:20 (*offerings made in the goren*), 2 Sam 6:6-11 (*correct goren for resting the ark*), 2 Chr 3:1 (*temple built upon the goren*). Heb. *gōren* is the cognate of Akk. *garānu* (*to heap up grain*). As a threshing floor and harvest shelter, it is equivalent to Akk. *maškanu*—cognate of Heb. *miškān* (*tabernacle*). *Maškanu* is expressed with the logogram LAGAR x ŠE—which is the sign for *lagaru* priest enclosing the sign for barley.

¹⁸ Schmidt notes the theophoric element *yrh* in Canaanite personal names Ebed-Yariḥ and Yariḥ-Ezer (*Moon*, p. 588). Bereshit Rabbah 98:17 cites the town of Beth-Jerah (*Bêt Yareah*).

¹⁹ In context, this designation may play on Akk. *zununnû*—a marriage gift from a father-in-law to the bridegroom.

Gospel of Matthew holds that Rahab became the wife of Salmon (Mat 1:5), making her the foundress of Bethlehem (see I Chr 2:51).

Like the matriarchs Sarah, Rebecca and Rachel of Ur/Harran, the *q̄dēšāh* Rahab of Jericho was taken away from the City of the Moon by the shepherd clan. Like Ruth, she made a dramatic choice to reject her own people and join another nation. Her city was annihilated. If we take a mental step back from the familiarity of these narratives, the critical roles played by each of these foreign women in the literary history of the nation is nothing less than astonishing. The motif of the stunningly beautiful priestess of the moon informs us that the scribes who recorded these narratives considered her essential to their purposes. We are compelled to ask “*Why?*”

3. The Entu in Mesopotamian History

In the era in which Sargon was born, Kiš was the ruling city state and Zababa was its patron deity. Ištar of Kiš (*Kiššītu*) was the divine consort of Zababa. After Sargon took the throne, he installed his daughter Enheduanna as *entu* in Ur. Both Enheduanna (c. 2300 BC) and Enannepadda (daughter of King Ur-Bau, c. 2100 BC) referred to themselves in inscriptions as “*wife of Nanna*” the moon god.³ In temple rites, the king acted in the role of the deity. His *entu* daughter became his ritual wife. Their union was consummated in the *giparu* of the temple of the goddess Ningal. This chamber was also called “*alcove of the warrior Sîn*”.³

According to Weadock, “*the celebration of the sacred marriage between Ningal and Sin was then the supreme purpose of the Ningal temple, a purpose clearly revealed by the plan of the temple and by the inscriptional material connected with the temple.*”³ Although king and daughter rarely conceived a viable child, the birth of a son to an *entu* mother marked him out as extraordinary heir destined for greatness. It was therefore utterly taboo for the *entu* to consort with another man and bear his child.

A rare example of a king born from an *entu* mother is Shulgi (r. 2094-2046 BC), the son of Ur-Nammu and his daughter (probably Ennirgalanna).³ Scholars have noted the seeming incongruity between the normal childless state of the *entu* priestess and the absence of social sanctions against Shulgi’s mother.²⁰ The appearance of contradiction is resolved with the understanding that the *entu* was allowed to bear the child of the king, who was her father (or very rarely her brother, if he assumed the kingship).

In Mesopotamia proper, the *entu* (or more precisely the *entu rabû*) was chosen from among the daughters of the king. This custom was practiced during the era extending from at least the reign of Sargon of Akkad to the dynasty of Nebuchadnezzar I (2300-1100 BC), and perhaps the following

²⁰ See Glassner, *Recit de Sargon*, p. 5. Beaulieu (*Reign of Nabonidus*, p. 71) cites an inscription of Adad-apl-iddina (r. 1064-1043) in which he calls himself “*son-in-law of Nanna*”—suggesting that he was born of an *entu* mother.

century. The entuship appears to have been abandoned in Ur during the Late Bronze Age Collapse. Nevertheless, there are indications that kings' daughters continued to serve as temple priestesses without being designated *entu*. In a late example, one of Nebuchanezzar II's daughters served as a priestess in the É-anna of Uruk.²¹

In 553 BC, Nabonidus (Akk. *Nabû-na'id*) of Harran took the throne of Babylon from Nebuchadnezzar's grandson. He revived the office of the *entu* of Ur after a half-millennium of abandonment. Nabonidus' patron god was Sîn (*aka* ^d30, ^dŠEŠ^{ki}).²² Like Sargon the Great and the Sargonid kings of Neo-Assyria, Nabonidus believed that the prosperity of the land and the empire was contingent upon the restoration of the moon god to his ancient prominence.²³ His worldview and reign appear to have been entirely based on this premise.

Nabonidus installed his daughter Ennigaldi (whom he called *beloved of my heart*) as *entu* in Ur, offering her to the moon god as his human wife.²⁴ However, Nabonidus himself became the warrior Sîn during the *hieros gamos*. Following the ancient tradition, Ennigaldi became her father's ritual wife in the fertility rites that took place in the temple of Ningal, which was part of the ziggurat complex of Ur that Nabonidus rebuilt.³ By reinstating this ancient custom, the usurping king established his divine right to be *šarru kiššati*—*King of All the Lands*.²³

As we shall see, the purpose of the recurring foreign woman in the Hebrew scriptures is closely tied to the events of the mid-6th century BC. It is precisely the foundational idea of the *entu* conferring the *šarrut kiššatim* (*kingship of all the lands*) upon Babylon that captured the full attention of the Judeans who served in the court of Nabonidus of Harran. His improbable rise to the throne and subsequent re-imposition of the ancient worship of the moon god were stunning developments. In a world of warring gods, the Judean scribes had every reason to believe that the nefarious power of Sîn was real.

4. A Missing Link and a Linking Idea

The eastern geographic setting of the opening episodes of in Genesis suggests that the biblical *entu* had a Mesopotamian inspiration. The religious reform of Nabonidus (r. 556-539 BC) took place in the midst of the 6th century Judean exile in Babylon. The priests of Marduk and the citizens

²¹ Kaššaya, daughter of Nebuchadnezzar, had a regular allotment (*quppu*) in the É-anna (Beaulieu, *Reign of Nabonidus*, p. 122).

²² Nabonidus was raised by his mother, who devoted her long life to Sîn. On the eve of the destruction of Harran by the Medes (609 BCE), she accompanied the cult statues brought to Babylon from Harran by Nabopolassar, which she venerated until Nabonidus fulfilled her dream and rebuilt the E₂.ĜUL₂.ĜUL₂ fifty some years later (Beaulieu, *Reign of Nabonidus*, pp. 68-79).

²³ For a discussion of the “*Era of the Moon-god*”, see Lewy, *Cult of the Moon*, pp. 462-464, 486-

²⁴ See Clay, *YOS I*(45), pp. 66-75.

of Babylon proper were shaken by the substitution of Sîn for Marduk as the head of the Mesopotamian pantheon.²⁵ This drama in the heart of the great empire could not have gone unnoticed by the Judeans of this era.

If we are searching for the most likely time, place and historical circumstance under which the concept of the *entu* entered the consciousness of the Judean scribes, this is it. The fact that Ur and Harran are named as the geographic origins of the archetypal Hebrew matriarchs is telling. It bears the hallmarks of the reign of Nabonidus. Hence, it appears that the skilled Judean scholar-scribes of Neo-Babylon set out to reverse their nation’s captivity by winning the power of the *entu* for their own people, thereby reciprocally transferring the *šarrut kiššatim* to the Davidic dynasty. They used Mesopotamian scribal magic and written ritual to establish a hiero-gamic chain extending back to the remote era of their shepherd ancestors, thereby staking their claim to the destiny sought by Nabonidus.

Although the biblical timeline assigns the matriarchs to the early and mid-second millennium, we do not have historical evidence of an ancestral migration from the East. To the contrary, the ethnic, linguistic, epigraphic and religious data demonstrate the presence of semi-nomadic clans such as the “*Shasu of Yhw*” in the desert area between Canaan and Egypt throughout the second millennium.²⁶ In Egyptian inscriptions, the word *yhw* (or *yh^w*) is followed by the determinative hieroglyph for a foreign land, making it a toponym.²⁷ In Hebraic tradition, the ancestral god YHWH is connected to the “*Mountain of Elohim*” in the remote desert (Exod 3:1-5, Jdg 5:3-5, 1 Kgs 19:8-9).²⁸ The body of evidence points to *Yhw* as the *genius loci* who inhabited this arid. He was the deity of the nomads who herded their livestock in this rugged land.

The archaeological record attests to the settlement of the Canaanite highlands during the century-long drought associated with the Late Bronze Age Collapse (1250-1100 BC).²⁹ The Yahwistic theophoric elements in the names of the newcomers connect them to the “*Shasu of Yhw*”. These tangible historical elements of the nation’s ancestry require a reclassification of the patriarchal cycle of Genesis. Instead of representing the ancestral memory and oral history of the nation, the stories belong to a different genre altogether. In fact, the narrative of Moses acknowledges that the patriarchs never knew the divine name Yhwh (Exod 6:3), reinforcing the sense of an eastern stratum interpolated into the ancestral record.

The *entu* may be the key to putting the pieces of this puzzle back to together correctly. In the mid-1st millennium BC, Nabonidus perceived the restoration of the ancient entuship as the

²⁵ Oppenheim, *Verse Account of Nabonidus*.

²⁶ See Avner, *Origin of Yhwh*.

²⁷ Kitchen, *Ramesside Inscriptions*, II #60 13.

²⁸ Upon hearing of Yahweh’s mighty deeds in Egyptian, Jethro (priest of Midian) marveled that his local god’s power extended to Egypt (Exod 18:11)—see Blenkinsopp, *Midianite-Kenite Hypothesis*, pp. 134-135.

²⁹ See Finkelstein, *Great Transformation* and Langgut et al., *Late Bronze Age Collapse*.

prerequisite for the resurrection of the empire of Sargon and the establishment of his own dynasty. Thus, the Hebraic “theft” of the *entu* from Ur/Harran may be understood as a logical (and extremely audacious) proposition by the Judean scribes who wrote Genesis. Their plan was set in motion in a written symbolic format. Jacob is literally Israel in ancestral form (Gen 32:28-32, 35:10-11). Jacob’s possession of the *entu* daughters of Laban resulted in the birth of 12 sons, each embodying a tribe of Israel. At the same time, Jacob’s flocks multiplied supernaturally, while the flocks of the White One decreased in inverse proportion (Gen 30:40-31:1). The wealth of Harran was symbolically transferred to the tribes of Israel.

In the context of 6th century Babylon, Jacob’s subsequent escape and return to the ancestral land with his 12 sons may be understood as an invocation of the return of the 12 tribes of Israel. In symbolic form, they were the exiles who were abducted from the northern (Leah) and southern kingdoms (Rachel). Although this account is narrated as ancient history, the archaeological record signals that the desert tribes of southern Canaan worshiped Yahweh before the arrival of the patriarchs in the biblical timeline (see Exod. 3:1, 6:2-3, 18: 12). If the future tribes of Israel were already present in the West, then their descendance from eastern Jacob (renamed Israel) is figurative rather than historical.

When we consider the nation’s West Semitic history in the light of the mid-1st millennium Mesopotamian motifs that permeate the narrative, the representational nature of the work comes into focus. In each episode of the ancestral account, the return of the shepherd clan to its homeland is called into being in symbolic form. This invocation follows the contemporary pattern of Ezekiel’s vision of a valley filled with dry bones. Ezekiel was a prophet-scribe of the Babylonian exile. When Ezekiel spoke, the skeletons reassembled and returned to life (Ezek 37:1-14). The prophet was not merely the witness of a miracle foretold in a dream. Instead, Ezekiel was the active agent who set this outcome in motion by prophesying (in written form) to the metaphorical dry bones of the nation, declaring that they would come back to life and return to their own land.

5. Scribal Invocation and Magical Double-entendres

Like the birth story of Moses, Ezekiel’s account of the bones did not arise in a literary vacuum. It was conceived and written in 6th century Mesopotamia, where the restoration of Babylon from ruins to its third era of glory was annually celebrated in the Akītu festival. This 12 day national holiday was observed by a public reading of the *Enuma Elish*—the national epic of Babylon. Although this celebration is often pictured as a triumphal celebration held in Babylon the Great, there is a detailed record its observance in Aššur by the priests of the cult of Marduk-in-Exile.³⁰ Babylon experienced centuries of disenfranchisement following various conquests. The cult statue of Marduk was carried

³⁰ Langdon, *Babylonian Epic*, pp. 32-50.

off to foreign lands multiple times. With this history in mind, the epic may be better understood as an invocation of Babylon's return to glory rather than a commemoration of it.

The scribe who wrote the Enuma Elish used the literary framework of a historical account to establish the cosmological basis for the rise of Babylon. He achieved this by retroactively inserting the rise of Marduk into the ancient tale of the battle between the gods and the primordial sea. At the end of the poem, the scribe identifies his composition as a repetition of the authoritative word of Marduk that he recorded “*for the future to hear*” (En el VII:158). The “future” was the author's temporal present viewed from the literary past. The scribe thus commanded destiny to deliver the nation's change of fate that he called into being.³¹

The skilled Mesopotamian scribe had an extensive toolbox for effecting textual magic. This included making use of the property of cuneiform signs to simultaneously express ideas (logograms) and sounds (syllabograms).³² Cuneiform was invented by the Sumerians and subsequently borrowed by the Akkadians, who employed the same symbols to represent their language. This means that Akkadian texts written in syllabic cuneiform have the capacity to express Sumerian motifs retained in the same signs. The same sign may represent different phonemes, while the same phoneme may be represented by different signs. In modern scholarly convention, these cuneiform variants are distinguished by transcribing them in Latin characters written with different numerical subscripts.

To those who have not studied cuneiform, this polyvalency may be extremely confusing. What is important to grasp is the unparalleled capacity of cuneiform to encode double-entendres. This flexibility underpins the scribal use of cuneiform signs to transmit both the simple surface meaning and critical information hidden beneath. It is reflected in many terms for word-craft in the Akkadian lexicon—including *lumāšu* (*twin-image*), *amāt niširti* (*hidden word*) and *niširti ummâni* (*secret lore of the scholars*).³³

In classical Mesopotamian works, the deployment of hidden meanings for magical purpose is often focused upon the act of naming. The Enuma Elish is the archetype of this literary genre.³² As explained by Benjamin Foster,

The poem begins and ends with concepts of naming ... For the poet, the name, properly understood, discloses the significance of the created thing. Semantic and phonological analysis of names could lead to understanding of the things named. Names, for this poet, are a text to be read by the informed.³¹

³¹ Foster notes that the author subtly takes scribal credit for aiding Marduk (*Before the Muses*, pp. 436-438).

³² See Bottéro, *Mesopotamia*, pp. 88-91, 229

³³ See Landsberger and Kinnier Wilson (*Fifth Tablet*), McHugh (*Celestial Cuneiform Puns*) and Noegel (*Wordplay*).

If we consider the Mesopotamian setting of the early chapters of Genesis and the considerable Mesopotamian literary influences upon the stories, it cannot be a coincidence that naming wordplays underlie all the patriarchal and matriarchal appellations. Significantly, many of these puns cannot be understood from the text handed down to us. The etymology of “Abraham” as the *father of many nations* makes no sense in Hebrew. Likewise, the derivation of *mother of all who live* from “Eve” (*Hwh*) requires a search of cognate languages. The mysterious name “Moses” is another example. In this case, however, we have a cuneiform parallel text to compare with. The fact that the Birth Legend of Sargon also features a woman acting to dethrone the reigning dynasty makes it the logical starting point for locating the time and place of the entry of the *entu* into biblical thought. This chronology is also critical for seeing through the Mosaic veil that obscures the history of ancient Israel.

6. Cryptic Naming in the Birth Account of Sargon

The biblical prevalence of the kind of nomenclatural wordplay that characterizes Mesopotamian epic poetry directs us to look closely at the names and naming of Sargon and Moses in their respective birth stories. Sargon (*šar-gi-na*) is named in the incipit of his own account. His naming phrase is comprised of a set of cuneiform double-entendres that encapsulates the plot of the story.

LUGAL.GI.NA, LUGAL dan-nu a-ga-de₃^{ki} a-na-ku
Sargon, mighty king of Agade am I

The logogram LUGAL is read aloud as *šar* or *šarru* (*king*) in Akkadian. However, in Sumerian *šar* can mean *to begin, to write, to insert, to enter* and *to drive away*. Gi signifies *reed, to surround* and *boy*, while na (as na₅) is a *chest* or *box*. GI.NA or GE.NA (Sum. *genna*, Akk. *ginû*) refers to a young child. The implied homophone ge₂₆-na is an imperative form meaning *go*—implicitly in a *basket* (Sum. *bisag* = ge₂₆).

The authoring scribe thus begins the story by using Sargon’s name to predict the events to come. More precisely, the scribe created the details of the plot by parsing the meanings of the signs comprising the great king’s name. The scribe facilitated his task by selecting syllabic signs carrying logographic meanings that fine-tuned his narrative purpose. In an homage to the learned scholar, the authoring scribe made his intervention in the story metafictionally transparent by beginning with a pun on the word *beginning*.³⁴

The main plot of the older Sumerian Legend revolves around Sargon’s divinely aided “theft” of the throne of Ur-Zababa. The author of the later Akkadian birth legend counteracts potential

³⁴ The sign SAR/ŠAR signifies “*to begin, start, inaugurate*” and “*to write down*” or “*inscribe*” a tablet (Akk. *šarrû*).

accusations of wrongful usurpation by discovering Sargon’s divine right to the kingship encoded in his name. Although many different spellings of the name Sargon are attested in Mesopotamian records, the author of this text employs LUGAL.GI.NA. Given the overriding theme of legitimacy and right to rule, a cluster of Sumerian meanings come into play. Gi can also signify *judgment* and *to establish something as the property of someone*. Na is *man*. These properties are attached to lugal, which is *king*. The logogram GI.NA (as Akk. *kanû*) means *to become permanent, firm, true*. Sargon’s right to the kingship is thereby elucidated from the logographic sequence, furnishing proof through divinely revealed word craft—which formed the secret lore of the scribes.

7. Cryptic Naming in the Birth Account of Moses

It is striking that the biblical narrative of Moses never gives the Hebrew birth name of the leader of the nation. Instead, it is the “Egyptian” princess who names him—ostensibly in her own language. He was already three months old when she found him (Exod 2:2-5). At the point in the narrative where we would expect a Hebrew name to appear, the narrator states that his birth mother *saw that he was good* (ותרא אתו כי טוב הוא). According to the scribal guide *Ochlah W’ochlah*, this adjective was to be recorded with an oversized ט (*t*), signifying a hidden meaning.³⁵ Talmudic commentators posited that “*Tob*” (or *Tob-yah*) was Moses’ true name.³⁶

The spatial arrangement of these phrases in the Leningrad Codex suggests that the master scribe Samuel ben Jacob recognized a symbolic linkage between the ostensible Hebrew and Egyptian names of Moses.

Figure 2. The three column arrangement of Exod 2 in the Leningrad Codex condenses some lines on the page and shortens others—creating an alignment of the putative Hebrew naming element *tob* with the presumed Egyptian name *mōšēh*. Pharaoh’s daughter in the second column is paired with Moses’ birth mother in the first. The drawing of the infant Moses from the water is aligned with the statement “*He saved us*” in the third column. Adapted from a Public Domain reproduction in the Internet Archive.

Although the rabbis and scribes perceived the nomenclatural nature of this textual nexus, the Hebrew word *tob* lacks a signification that compellingly rises to the stature of Moses’ greatness. It

³⁵ See Frensdorff, *Das Buch*, #88. The oversized *tet* is not present in the MT.

³⁶ Sotah 12a:17 connects “*Tob*” with Moses’ calling as a prophet.

does not define Moses in the manner that LUGAL.GI.NA defines Sargon. Intriguingly, the two letter root *tb* (in the syllabic form $\text{ti}_2\text{-ib}$) occurs in the Birth Legend of Sargon at the narrative juncture corresponding to where Moses receives his “Egyptian” name.

7. id-dan-ni a-na ID₂ ša₂ la e-le-e-a
She consigned me to the river from which I could not rise.
8. iš-ša₂-an-ni ID a-na UGU ^{lu}aq-qi A.BAL u-bil-an-ni
The river carried me, to Akki the water drawer it brought me.
9. ^{lu}aq-qi₂ A.BAL i-na $\text{ti}_2\text{-ib}$ da-li-šu₂ u₂-še-la-an-ni
Akki the water drawer by submerging his bucket raised me up.

Figure 1. The Birth Legend of Sargon, lines 7-9. The actions of the *entu* and the water drawer mirror each other—one places the child in the water, the other removes him. The text concomitantly juxtaposes the ideas of the infant hero being submerged ($\text{ti}_2\text{-ib} = \text{tebû}$) and the future king ($\text{ti}_2 = \text{šar}_2$) rising up (*tebû*). Hand copy by L.W. King (CT XIII, Plate 42) of a 7th century BC tablet found in Ashurbanipal’s Library, Nineveh. The Latin transcription and English translation are adapted from Lewis (*Sargon Legend*). Missing or indistinct signs are completed from other copies.

The Hebrew and Akkadian plots run parallel to each other, making the cuneiform semantic field of *tb* contextually relevant. Given the constitutive wordplay of the older text, we must consider looking to cuneiform for the missing birth name of the Hebrew hero. The syllables $\text{ti}_2\text{-ib}$ represent the verb *tebû* (*to submerge*). As noted earlier, each cuneiform sign acquired additional phonetic values over time. In this case, Akkadian $\text{ti}_2\text{ ib}$ is Sumerian $\text{šar}_2\text{ uraš}$ (*~secret king*) and $\text{dug}_3\text{ uraš}$ (*good secret*). The homophonic *ti.ib* signifies *life secret* or *hidden life*. This symbolic sequence from the cuneiform source is reprised in the Hebrew text of Exodus. Moses’ birth mother hid him when she saw that he was *ṭob* (*good*).

The Levite woman placed him in a basket-like vessel made of reeds, which is identified as a “*tebah*” (תבה). The only other occurrence of this term in the Hebrew scriptures is the “Ark” of Noah—another story with direct Mesopotamian literary roots. It is generally recognized that *tah* is a Hebrew spelling of a non-Hebrew word.³⁷ This confluence underscores the sense that the *tb/tb*

³⁷ See Finkel, *Ark Before Noah*, p. 197.

lexeme possesses cryptic meanings in Genesis-Exodus—as signaled by the oversized **ט** prescribed in *Ochlah W'ochlah*.

The Akkadian cognate of *ṭob* is *ṭābu*. In our parallel birth texts, *ṭābu* evokes the homophonic antonyms *ṭebû* (*to drown, sink, submerge*) and *tabû* (*to get up, arise, set out*). *Tabû* is also used in the context of rebellions, which both Sargon and Moses later lead. Significantly, *tabû* is expressed with the logogram ZI, meaning “*life*” in Sumerian. *Tabû* was sometimes written with the alternative logogram I.ZI.A, which can be read as an expression of the sum of its Sumerian parts: *i* (*to remove, take away, to bring out*), *zi* (*life*) and *a* (*water/nominative*). These lexemes and their ideograms are acted out in both the Sargonic and Mosaic accounts (and in the Ark stories of Atrahasis and Noah).³⁸

If the etymological disambiguation proposed here was made in a vacuum, it could be labeled as arbitrary or merely speculative. However, the Hebrew text is modeled upon the Sargonic text in which the infant hero’s future is predicted from his name. This informs us that a similar pattern in the birth story of Moses is not only possible, but should be expected. Just as the narrative naming of Sargon uses double meanings to foretell events, so *ṭābu* (*good*) predicts *tabû*—the *arising* of the Hebrew rebel leader Moses.

Readers with a literal mindset may object that the word “*ṭob*” is used as an adjective and not as Moses’ name, which is clearly stated several lines later. However, the *entu* role in the birth story of Moses is divided between two women. One put the boy into the river, the other (like Akki) took him out. This mirroring suggests that “*ṭob*” (Akk. *ṭābu*) belongs to the first part of Moses’ naming, which is then completed by the second *entu*. The interrelationship of this pairing can be seen in the statement of Pharaoh’s daughter, “*for from the water I drew him*” (כי מין המים מישיתרו) —which precisely reprises the meaning of I.ZI.A (*tabû*).

The birth story of Moses credits Pharaoh’s daughter with coining a unique personal name derived from the circumstances in which she discovered him. The name should therefore be Egyptian, yet the narrative confusingly provides a Hebrew etymology. Scholars have long suspected this etymology as an alibi meant to obscure an original Egyptian name by removing the theophoric element (e.g. Ra, Thoth) of his name and developing a cover story for the residual suffix *-mose* (meaning *born of*).³⁹ However, this assumes the existence of a historical 2nd millennium Moses. As noted previously, there is no material evidence of the name Moses from before the exile, nor does the archaeological record support the public practice of the Mosaic Law in antiquity.

If we grasp the post-exilic emergence of Moses and combine this knowledge with the fact his birth account derives from a story that was written in Akkadian, it tells us to look to the literary

³⁸ The logogram ZI (Akk. *napištu*) is present in the name of the Sumerian flood hero (UD.ZI-tim—*Utnapištim*) and in the Akkadian name of the Ark (*Naširat Napištim—Preserver of Life*).

³⁹ Carroll, *Moses’ Name*, p. 775.

language of Mesopotamia for answers. The etymological statement “*from the water I drew him*” plays upon Akkadian *mû* (*water*) and Sumerian *mu* (*son*). If the name *mšh* (משה) is a consonantal transcription of syllabic Akkadian, then *mu* is the first syllable (or prefix). The stem *šh* comprising the semantic core of his name can be reconstructed by syllabic expansion to Akkadian *šēhu*—which means *ecstatic* or *prophet*.⁴⁰ משה (*Mu-šēhu*) is the *Son of the prophet*—an expression well-attested in the Hebrew scriptures. In narrative context, his title identifies his *entu* mother(s) as prophetess(es).

The homophone *sēhu* signifies *to rise up* and *revolt*. By extension, the form *musehû* refers to one who foments rebellion. This double-entendre confirms the foretelling of Moses’ birth mother, who “*saw*” that the child was *ṭob* (*ṭābu* → *tabû*—*to rise up in rebellion*). She then concealed him as a direct consequence of her vision. At the end of the period of concealment, the oracle of his birth mother was confirmed in the name given by his adoptive mother. Thus, the personal name Moses (coined by the scribe acting as *entu*) not only fits the etymology she articulates, but also identifies his future actions and office—following the template of LUGAL.GI.NA.

If we overlay the Mosaic and Sargonic accounts and read them as a composite text, Pharaoh’s daughter takes the place of Akki (*ak-ki*), the water-drawer who discovers Sargon in the floating basket. His name is written with the sign AG (= AK), which is the logogram for *nabû*—*to name, to call, to nominate for office*. In Hebrew, *nābî* (נבי) is a prophet. The Akkadian cognate *nābû* (a type of diviner) is attested from Mari and Emar.⁴¹ Ki is the cuneiform determinative for a geographic place. Thus, Pharaoh’s daughter names Moses in the exact narrative location of AG^{ki} (*Place of Naming/Place of the Prophet*) in the source text.⁴²

Viewed without prejudice, this precise correspondence informs us that the original author of the birth story of Moses in Exodus worked directly from the tablet of Birth Legend of Sargon. Concomitantly, it shows that the author was a competent and accomplished cuneiform scribe. The Book of Daniel tells the story of four exceptional young Judeans trained in “*the literature and language of the Chaldeans*” (Dan 1:3-4). Irving Finkel notes that Neo-Babylonian scribal schools required pupils to hand-copy cuneiform tablets of classic works—including the Birth Legend of Sargon (and the Ark story).⁴³ This anecdote gives us a sense of the educational opportunities and upward mobility available to exceptionally talented Judean exiles under the Neo-Babylonian administration. It also presents us with the only known place, time and circumstances under which Judean scribes studied the lore of Mesopotamia that reappears in Genesis and Exodus—with details changed to fit Hebraic circumstances.

⁴⁰ More commonly written *šēhānu*. The CDA cites the form *ša šēhi*, referring to an ecstatic.

⁴¹ Fleming (*Origins of Hebrew Nābî*) states that the title *nābî* designated “*the One Who Invokes God*”.

⁴² The phrase “*ana UGU¹ aq-qī*” (line 8) is read “*ana muḥḥi¹ aq-qī*” (Lewis, *Sargon Legend*, p. 25), which the Judean scribe took as “*ana muḥḥû ana AG^{ki}*”—*destiny* (*ana* = NAM) *of a prophet against the place of Nabû*.

⁴³ See Finkel (*Ark Before Noah*).

8. Paradigm Shifts

When longstanding beliefs are challenged with new information and ideas, the normal response is to ignore the intrusion. If this dismissal fails, a hard push-back can be expected.⁴⁴ This is no less true of academia than it is of communities of faith. In either case, when cherished ideas appear threatened, they are either dismissed out of hand or vehemently rejected, with the proposer pilloried as an abjectly uniformed meddler in settled matters. It is to be expected that readers raised with the belief that the Hebrew scriptures are exact historical facsimiles will see heresy in the alternative interpretation presented here. Meanwhile, scholars commenting on earlier versions of this analysis raised the objection that the thesis rests upon language speculations that cannot be proven—making it a pointless exercise.

Against this, it may be argued that neither traditional religious views (such as 2nd millennium Moses in Egypt) nor established scholarly paradigms (such as the oral transmission of patriarchal traditions that were eventually recorded in writing) are objectively grounded in history. They fail to account for many striking features of the Hebrew scriptures—such as the recurring foreign woman bearing the chosen child or the symbolic importance of the recurring number 40 or why the patriarchs did not know the name Yahweh when they called upon him by name. New answers are needed that do not rely upon old assumptions, but rather reflect the archaeology and the accessible textual history. Perhaps most importantly, scriptural stories must be understood within the time, place and culture in which they were composed rather than through the lens of later thought. This necessarily requires using the same semiotic tools the scribes employed to compose the stories in the first place. If this is dismissed as an unattainable goal, then the pieces of the puzzle cannot be assembled and joined.

As remarked in the introduction, most scholarly analyses of the Mosaic and Sargonic origin accounts digress into discussions of the heroic literature or the foundling child myth.⁵ This approach offers little that is new or practically useful. In a rare departure from this formula, Eckart Otto noted that the vocabulary and phraseology of the Akkadian source story gives it a Neo-Assyrian time stamp.⁴⁵ Otto then recognized that the dependence of the birth story of Moses upon the Birth Legend of Sargon imposes an absolute historical time boundary: the literary origin of Moses cannot predate the Neo-Assyrian era.⁴⁵ Given the Mosaic structure through which the Hebrew scriptures are traditionally understood, this chronological epiphany lifts the Mosaic veil covering the ancient religious culture of the nation.

If key protagonists in the history of the Hebrew nation were in fact representational figures acting within their own stories, the entire historical picture shifts. It is likely (or at least highly

⁴⁴ See Kuhn, *Scientific Revolutions*.

⁴⁵ Otto (*Die Geburt des Mose*, p. 24) notes the presence of words and formulaic phrases in the Birth Legend of Sargon that only occur in Neo-Assyrian literature.

plausible) that the birth story of Sargon the Great was composed on behalf of Sargon II, who seized the throne of Shalmaneser V in 722 BC.⁷ This conclusion is based upon the shared name Sargon, the central motif of the divine right to rule and its correspondence to a political event that occurred during the approximate era of composition. If this 8th century *coup d'état* was in fact the motivation for adding a prequel to the Sargon legend, it means that the literary inspiration for Moses' birth account had a subversive allegorical dimension. It is a feature that we should fully expect to find in the Hebraic adaptation of this story.

This literary dependence upon a Neo-Assyrian allegory is a massive “tell”. It means that the Moses we know was conceptually shaped by a cultural contact that occurred at a completely different point on the biblical timeline. Moreover, this reality concomitantly informs us that the Egyptian setting of Moses cannot be historical, but must instead be a retrospective projection. Otto concludes that the Mosaic theme of liberation was a Judean response to 7th century Neo-Assyrian imperialism with its imposition of *corvée* labor upon the conquered peoples:

The author ... of the Exodus of Moses projects the forced labor of the neo-Assyrian hegemonic power onto the fictitious situation of Israel in Egypt and in this way makes the (allegory of the) events at the time of Moses in Egypt transparent to the audience for Moses' exodus tales in the 7th century BC. Eckart Otto (*Die Geiburt des Mose*, p. 25, translated from German)

Otto identifies multiple biblical passages that draw upon Neo-Assyrian oracles and legal documents. Nevertheless, his *terminus ad quem* is too early. Otto's conclusions require Judean mastery of cuneiform at a time (the late 7th century BC) and a place (Jerusalem) for which we have no archaeological evidence for this level of foreign cultural adoption and access to cuneiform source documents. In contrast, we have extensive evidence that communities of Judean deportees in Babylonia adopted Akkadian cuneiform as their medium for keeping written records in the 6th century BC.⁴⁶ In other words, the incorporation of Neo-Assyrian material only imposes the requirement that the Hebrew texts cannot precede them. It must be kept in mind that archived Neo-Assyrian tablets were accessible to 6th century Judean scribes educated in Babylon and employed in the royal service (see Dan 1:3-4, 2:48-49).

Although the birth narrative of Moses was adapted from the Neo-Assyrian Birth Legend of Sargon, this tablet was used as a scribal training text in Neo-Babylon.⁴³ The Hebraic version makes significant changes that align with 6th century developments—especially the restoration of the entuship of the empire.⁴⁷ The understated role of Sargon's *entu* mother is augmented in the

⁴⁶ See Pearce and Wunsch, *Documents of Judean Exiles*.

⁴⁷ The Neo-Assyrian political context of Moses posited by Otto lacks a contemporary context for the *entu*. Although Otto makes the connection between Sargon's unnamed *entu* mother in the literary account and

Hebraic adaptation. The water-drawer Akki is transformed into Pharaoh’s daughter. It is she who declares the enigmatic name of the pivotal figure of Hebrew history. As argued in the previous section, משה (*Mšh* < Akk. *Mušēhu*) was literally coined by a Mesopotamian *entu* in Egyptian guise. She named him as she drew him forth from the water (*mû*) at the Place of Naming/Place of the Prophet (Akki = AG^{ki} = Nabû^{ki} ~ Šēḥu^{ki}). If we accept that Moses came into being as a revolutionary figure in the minds of Judean scribes of the Babylonian exile, then his *entu* mother(s) must be an integral part of this theme. Her centrality to the Hebraic narrative of liberation firmly anchors the core biblical account in 6th century Neo-Babylon.

9. Egypt as Babylon

If we set aside the longstanding assumption that מצרים (*miṣrāyīm*, Akk. *muṣrī*) is geographical Egypt, the underlying motivation for the Judean adaptation of the Sargonic account emerges. The 1st millennium Mesopotamian literary source of Moses and the late date of emergence of Mosaic practices in the popular culture signal that the location of the Exodus is allegorical. In other words, biblical slavery in “Egypt” in antiquity is a metaphor for contemporary slavery in 6th century Neo-Babylon. This inference is supported by hints elsewhere that biblical “Egypt” refers to two different places, depending on context—as suggested by the Hebrew suffix.⁴⁸

A parallel passage signals that the “Egypt” of Moses and the parting of the Sea is a coded reference to a different land of captivity:

And with thee will I break in pieces the horse and his rider; and with thee will I break in pieces the chariot and his rider ... The sea is come up upon Babylon: she is covered with the multitude of the waves thereof ... My people, go ye out of the midst of her. ... Thus shall Babylon sink, and shall not rise from the evil that I will bring upon her.

Jer 51:21, 42, 45, 64, KJV

A striking aspect of “Pharaoh” (פרעה) in the Hebrew narratives of Genesis and Exodus is that the king is never named. He appears in multiple generations of the ancestral saga of Israel. His appearances comprise a repeating pattern centered upon the *entu*. These generational iterations

Sargon’s historical *entu* daughter Enheduanna (*Die Geiburt des Mose*, p. 24), he does not perceive the recurring figure of this princess-priestess in the tapestry of the biblical narrative. Consequently, she has no role in the 7th century socio-political allegory he reconstructs from the text.

⁴⁸ The Heb. word for Egypt is always in the suffixed form *mšrym*. The apparent allusion to a pair (*-ayim*) is often understood to connote Upper and Lower Egypt, which existed as separate kingdoms until they were united under one crown. Na’aman (*Shaaraim*, pp. 2-3) argues that *-ayim/n* is a locative suffix in place names. If so, it would not have inhibited scribes from employing wordplays with hidden meanings derived from the plural appearance (e.g. Gen 46:27, Jos 2:10, 1 Kgs 12:28, 1 Chr 5:10).

repeat distinctive details in the interactions between the unnamed Egyptian ruler and ostensibly different women. After Sarai was taken into Pharaoh's harem, Egypt was struck by plagues (Gen 12:14-13:2). When she left Egypt after rejoining Abram, their clan was laden with silver and gold. This sequence is repeated in the story of Moses, with its 10 plagues and the riches bestowed upon the departing Hebrews by the Egyptians. Although the fate of Pharaoh's daughter is not disclosed in the Mosaic account, she reappears in the genealogy of Judah (1 Chr 4:18) as *Bat-yah* (בתיה).⁴⁹ This means that she left Egypt with the twelve tribes.

Their departure began at midnight on 15th of Nisan, which is the night of the full moon in the standardized Babylonian lunar calendar. In Mesopotamia, the phases of the moon were not merely calendrical markers. They were manifestations of the magical influence of the moon god Sîn upon the world of men stretched out below.⁵⁰ The nation left Egypt under complete darkness on the night of the full moon. Implicitly, the moon was eclipsed (cuneiform AN.MI—*sky darkness*). We get a sense of just how ominous this event was in Mesopotamian culture by the fact that King Esarhaddon of Assyria ritually abandoned the throne at least four times during eclipses.⁵¹ The Exodus account itself emphasizes that the nation departed under the pall of death. In Mesopotamia, this threat reached its sinister zenith under the darkened full moon.

The *entu* of Ur embodied Ningal, wife of the moon god. Since the human *entu* was the daughter-wife of the king, her divine homolog was Ištar, daughter of Sîn. In this sense, the two goddesses merged in the body of the high priestess. Since Moses was the son of the reigning *entu*, he implicitly had protection from the moon's deathly power. The decision of the *entu* (in the guise of Pharaoh's daughter) to leave "Egypt" implicitly signals the transfer of her allegiance and divine protection. Her Hebrew name *Bat-yah* substitutes the theophoric element *yah* for the logogram of Sîn in the title of the *entu* (see below). Her departure with the nomadic tribes of Israel subtly repeats the ancestral pattern of the tent-dwellers Abraham, Isaac and Jacob. In each iteration, this change of allegiance results in the reciprocal rise of the fortunes of the shepherd clan that set forth from Ur/Harran.

This repeating pattern is one of many reasons to consider Nabonidus the prime suspect for the unnamed villain of the Exodus—the long sought "Pharaoh of Moses". The fear of this tyrannical king during the putative mid-6th century era of composition of these accounts provides a compelling reason for the allegorical substitution. In fact, this substitution is absolute: Nabû-na'id is never mentioned by name in the canonical Hebrew scriptures, despite his critical role in the historical events at the conclusion of the exile.

⁴⁹ Vocalized as *bīt-yah* in the Masoretic text. The Talmud identifies her husband as Caleb (Sanhedrin 19b:15), as signaled in the genealogy of Judah. Curiously, Caleb has no ancestry beyond being the son of Jephunneh.

⁵⁰ Sîn (esp. as *Il-Teri* of Nabonidus) was also a chthonic deity who wielded power from below. He was the firstborn son of Enlil, begotten via rape, and the elder brother of Nergal, lord of the underworld.

⁵¹ Esarhaddon underwent the *bīt rimki* substitute king ritual each time (Bottéro (Mesopotamia, pp. 138-155).

The Judean scribal decision to replace Nabonidus with “Pharaoh” may have been inspired by his contemporary, Aḥmose II (r. 570–526 BC). His name honors the Egyptian moon god *Aah*, making him a very suitable proxy for the moon-besotted tyrant of Babylon. The Mesopotamian moon god was commonly invoked by his logogram ^dŠEŠ^{ki}, which may also be read as ^dAḤ₂^{ki}—reinforcing the conceptual link between the Babylonian monarch and his Egyptian homolog.

If the account of the drowning of Pharaoh and his army in the sea was an invocation of Nabonidus’ downfall, then it had to be hidden. At the same time, the written ritual enacting this curse needed to closely correspond to reality in order to be effective. In Babylonian magic, clay figurines were imbued with the identity of an enemy and thrown into fire or water.⁵² The Judean assimilation of this practice is attested in a ritual attributed to the prophet Jeremiah. He magically invoked Babylon’s demise by instructing a messenger to throw the inscription of a drowning curse (bound to a stone) into the Euphrates (Jer 51:61-63, curse quoted above). We may infer that the efficacy of this ritual in narrative form required that the proxy pharaoh of Exodus bear an accurate resemblance to the Babylonian king who was the true object of the curse.

If the hard-hearted Egyptian tyrant of the Exodus was modeled after Nabonidus, then it stands to reason that “Pharaoh’s daughter” was modeled after his daughter. In other words, the ritual requirement of correspondence to the real world must also hold true for the various matriarchal guises of the *entu*. These women share a remarkable geographical profile with Ennigaldi of Ur, daughter of Nabonidus of Harran.

Although we have no physical description of this princess, we may infer from her selection as high priestess that she was a rare beauty, fit to be the human wife of the moon god. Her regnal name En-nig₂-al-di-^dŠEŠ^{ki} signifies *Priestess desired by Šîn*. The Sumerian phrase nig₂-al-di (Akk. *erištu*) connotes sexual desire, while ni₂-gal means *awe-inspiring radiance*. In the imputed biblical parallel, each of the matriarchs from Ur-Harran was extraordinarily beautiful and physically desirable. The signs forming the name Ennigaldi can also be read as *Bêl-ša-al-ti*, where *ša’iltu* designates a female diviner and *šalātu* means *to have authority* in a matter.⁵³ This aspect of her persona corresponds to the “seeing” of Moses’ birth mother and to the divine revelation given to Rebecca of Harran—the figurative mother of Israel (Gen 25:22-23, 27:6-33). Each foresaw the destiny of her chosen son and acted to protect this future.

While Pharaoh is the archetypal evil tyrant who seeks to destroy Israel, his daughter unexpectedly devoted herself to saving an enslaved people. In multiple biblical appearances of the *entu*, the daughter rebels against her father and joins the shepherd clan that he oppresses. If these 1st millennium repetitions of the same core story were conceived as a contemporary allegory, then

⁵² The CAD cites an extensive magical vocabulary associated with this practice.

⁵³ See Clay (YOS I, 45) for this reading of her name. Rev. Clay contended that “*the entu were devoted to the practice of magic*”—especially divination (p. 68). Note that the idea of the *bêl šāl* is present in the story of Balaam, whose authoritative oracle is called *māšal* (Num 24:2-3).

the implicit confidence placed in a foreign princess by the Judean scribes suggests that a real life person inspired their 6th century hope for national restoration.

The discovery of a museum housing ancient artifacts (labeled in three languages) in the mid 6th century stratum of Ennigaldi's temple at Ur reveals a bright, highly educated mind with a keen interest in the history of civilizations.⁵⁴ The existence of this museum in antiquity is remarkable—and yet not altogether surprising given Ennigaldi's eccentric father, who dug up ancient ruins while seeking relics of the moon god. It is likely that she was raised by her grandmother—a veritable force-of-nature who devoted herself to the practice and preservation of ancient rites.⁵⁵ Nabonidus himself was a maverick who became one of history's most enigmatic kings. Perhaps we should not be surprised if his gifted and beautiful daughter developed a mind of her own.

10. The Return of the Entu

The rescuing deeds of Pharaoh's daughter are reprised by Esther, set in the Persian era. In her eponymous story, Esther foiled the plot of the vizier Haman to destroy the Jews. The name חַמָּן is the Hebrew consonantal equivalent of the cuneiform logogram HAMAN—an obscure cognomen of the Neo-Babylonian logogram MUATI (Akk. *Nabû*).⁵⁶ The sign is more commonly known as PA, representing the royal scepter or staff (Akk. *haṭṭu*). The homophone *haṭû* means *criminal* and *to do wrong, commit a crime*. These meanings correspond to the royal connections and the moral character and the villain. In the context of a meticulously crafted story in which multiple aspects of the plot come together perfectly, the name Haman (which is known only from the story of Esther) is a certainly a deliberate narrative choice.

The plot thickens with the knowledge that this sign was used by Nabonidus as his signature logogram on royal monuments. The cliff face of Sela in Edom preserves the image of this Babylonian king holding a staff, accompanied by a victory inscription signed ^dMUATI.I (pronounced *Nabû-na'id*).⁵⁷ This suggests that the personal name Haman is a clever allegorical substitution for Nabonidus. Intriguingly, there may be a historical basis for a literary second act in which the Babylonian king was reconceived as a rogue Persian official. According to the Greco-Babylonian

⁵⁴ See Woolley, UET IX, 16-17. The excavator also identified a scribal school that he believed was connected to the Neo-Babylonian display of ancient artifacts.

⁵⁵ Beaulieu (*Reign of Nabonidus*, pp. 69-79) notes that Adad-guppi (Ennigaldi's irrepressible grandmother) relocated to Babylon with her son Nabu-na'id when Harran (the last Neo-Assyrian capital) was sacked by the Medes. Her qualities were such that she appears to have charmed both the Assyrian rulers and Nebuchadnezzar II, from whom she won a place for her son in the royal court. This background suggests that the future Ennigaldi would have grown up in her grandmother's household in Babylon.

⁵⁶ See Labat (*Manuelle d'Épigraphie*, #295) and Šaškova (*CSL*).

⁵⁷ Crowell, *Nabonidus at as-Sila*, p. 82.

historian Berossus, Nabonidus was not killed by the Persians, but instead appointed governor of the province of Carmania, where he served under Cyrus, Cambyses and Darius.⁵⁸

Whether or not Esther and Haman have a tangible historical link to the Achaemenid dynasty, the presence of a heroine acting as a critical ally in the royal palace is part of a repeating pattern. Like Michal (who saved David from King Saul’s attempt to murder him) or Rahab (who hid the Israelite spies from the king of Jericho) or Sarai (who protected Abram from within Pharaoh’s harem), Esther acted from a vulnerable yet powerful position. Like Pharaoh’s daughter, Esther used her access to the authority of the kingship to turn the tables in favor of her chosen people. The royal decree of death was transformed to a guarantee of future life. Esther’s story may be understood as a post-exilic “update” of the allegory of the nation’s deliverance from Pharaoh—set in Persia instead of Egypt.⁵⁹ These repetitions beg the question of why this formula held such a deep appeal to the authoring scribes.

The answer proposed and discussed above is that the stories allegorically allude to persons and events in 6th century Neo-Babylon.⁶⁰ However, the authoring scribes’ profound belief in the divine and their passionate appeals for divine rescue point to an additional possibility—one that lies heretically outside the bounds of the monotheistic Judaism that emerged later. Esther’s name and her dazzling beauty identify her as the embodiment of Ištar (^dEš₄-tar₂). As such, Esther was not merely human, but also the arbiter of the power of this goddess. In Mesopotamian ritual, Ištar was invoked for divine protection in her heavenly manifestation as *Sebettu* (the constellation of the Pleiades, called *the Seven* and the *Star of Stars*). The supplicant addressed the goddess with the words, “*For the destruction of the wicked did Anu (deified Heaven) beget you*”.⁶¹ This liturgical appeal draws upon a multi-level wordplay in which *sebettu* (*seven*) is augmented by the homophones *šabbiṭu* (*scepter*) and *šabāṭu* (*to sweep away evil*).⁶²

⁵⁸ Cited by Beaulieu (*Reign of Nabonidus*, p. 231).

⁵⁹ If this self-styled master of arcane knowledge discovered that Judean scribes in his court (abetted by his own daughter) had written elaborate curses invoking his downfall, his motive for revenge-seeking as a Persian governor is clear. Haman used magic in his attempt to destroy the Jews (Est 3:7, 9:24). His casting of the *pur* corresponds to Akk. *purussû* (*omenological verdict*), while evoking *parāsu* (*to decide, cut off*), *parāṣu* (*perform a rite*) and *Paras* (*Persia*).

⁶⁰ The corollary of the allegorical identification of Pharaoh with Neo-Babylonian Nabonidus is that his daughter Ennigaldi played a role in his downfall. Although we have no historical evidence for her participation in his demise, the abrupt collapse of the Neo-Babylonian empire and the uncontested entry of the rebel Ugbaru (not Cyrus as is commonly reported) into Babylon in 539 BC indicates an “inside job” involving multiple highly placed Babylonians.

⁶¹ See Jimenez, *Bīt salā’ mē* liturgy (*New Fragments*, p. 108).

⁶² This invocation of Ištar also plays upon the homophony of Sum. *imin* (*seven*) and *inim* (*word, command, decree, oath*). A similar duality occurs in Heb. *šeba*^c (see Gen 21:27-31) and its derivative *šabāṭ* (Exod. 31:14-16). The Judean scribes of Babylon would have noted that the homophone *šibittu* means captivity. The

This symbolism plays a pivotal role in the narrative of Esther. The evil plot of Haman was completely reversed by the act of the king holding out his golden scepter to the queen (see Est 4:11, 5:2, 8:4-7).⁶² The authoring scribe employs many Akkadianisms, demonstrating familiarity with cuneiform.⁶³ Thus, in the context of Haman’s decree to destroy the Jews, the Hebrew spelling (אסתר) of the heroine’s name (ʾstr instead of ʾštr) may be deliberate—reflecting the conceptualization of the goddess’ name as a Sumerian title combining the sign for *curse* (ES₄) paired with the verb *to disperse* (TAR).⁶⁴

The Scroll of Esther famously fails to mention Yahweh.⁶⁵ The rabbinic consensus from the Talmudic era to the present holds that the omission of Yahweh’s name is a deliberate narrative device meant to draw attention to his unseen protective presence in the darkness of exile.⁶⁶ However, in the (Sumerian) Legend of Sargon, it is the goddess Ištar who guides (behind-the-scenes) the improbable series of events that lead inexorably to Sargon’s ascent to the throne. The (Akkadian) Birth Legend adds the backstory of Sargon’s birth to an *entu* mother. As the living representation of the goddess, the priestess’ act of placing her son in the river is ritually infused with the guarantee of Ištar’s protection. The Judean scribe who adapted this story certainly knew this. Moreover, neither the author of core Exodus nor the author of Esther had reason to remove the hand of the goddess.

The public worship of a goddess in Jerusalem may be inferred from a Judean silver coin minted during the Persian era. It depicts a woman’s helmeted head with an owl on the opposite face, bearing an Old Hebrew inscription of the name of the high priest Yohanan (YHD 25, Israel Numismatic Society).⁶⁷ The coin is modeled upon contemporary (but much finer) Greek coins depicting the warrior Athena and her animal messenger.⁶⁷

This imagery contrasts sharply with Josephus’ account of the mass public disturbance that arose over trophies displaying “images of men” awarded during King Herod’s games in the Jerusalem amphitheatre (Antiq XV:8:2), three centuries later. These were taken to be a violation of the commandment “*to not make the image of any living creature to worship it*” (Antiq III:5:5), even though the trophies were not worshiped. The juxtaposition testifies to a radical change in the Judean religion and religious mindset between the Persian and Hasmonean eras.

apotropaic cluster of *sebetu/šibittu/šabātu* may have conceptually influenced the conception of the weekly *šabāt* holiday.

⁶³ Tawill (*Akkadian Biblical Lexicon*) cites multiple occurrences in this scroll, although many more are missed.

⁶⁴ According to Labat (*Manuelle d’Épigraphie*, #339), es₄ = aš₂.

⁶⁵ The commentary *Esther Rabbah* interpolates the intervention of “*the Holy One blessed be He*” 110 times, consciously compensating for his narrative absence.

⁶⁶ Steinsalz (*Introduction to Esther*) refers to this guidance as “*the hidden hand of Divine Providence that pulls the strings in the story*”.

⁶⁷ See Adler, *Origins of Judaism*, p.198-205.

Athena was the Greek cognate of Canaanite Anat.⁶⁸ Both are western variations of Ištar. A deity called *Anat-Yahu* (Ara. ענתיהו) was worshiped in the 5th century Judean temple in Elephantine in upper Egypt.⁶⁹ The Elephantine community leaders corresponded with a high priest in Jerusalem named Yohanan.⁶⁹ In this light, the contemporary minting of a temple coin connecting the high priest of Jerusalem to the symbols of this goddess signals that she was officially recognized and venerated by Judeans during the Persian era.⁷⁰

If the post-exilic author of Esther lived prior to the Hasmonean religious revolution, then he (or she) had no theological obligation to insist upon the worship of Yahweh alone—which was instituted as part of the “Law of Moses” that emerged as public practice only after the rise of the Maccabean priest-kings. Quite the contrary, they had reason to celebrate the goddess. In the mythology of 2nd millennium Ugarit in the northern Levant, Anat slew the mighty sea serpent Yam (see KTU 1.3). The prophet Isaiah alludes to this event while calling all upon the great goddess for divine rescue:

Awaken! Awaken! Don strength, Arm of Yahweh,⁷¹
 Awaken as in ancient days, generations of old.
 Are you (fem. sing.) not She who hewed Rahab,
 Slew the Sea Serpent? Isa 51:9⁷²

⁶⁸ See Day, *Anat*. A bilingual inscription from Cyprus records *Anat* in Phoenician and *Athena* in Greek.

⁶⁹ See Crowley, *Aramaic Papyri*. Temple funds were assigned to this goddess and to Anat-Beyt-El (Ara. ענתביתאל), suggesting two cultic forms of Anat (a practice known elsewhere, such as the three forms of Inanna worshiped in the É-anna of Uruk, each with her own cella and statue).

⁷⁰ Alder (*Origins of Judaism*, 199) notes that there is no tangible evidence supporting the traditional presumption that the cultic activities of the priests serving in the Jerusalem temple in antiquity “conformed with anything resembling the rules and regulations outlined in the Pentateuch”.

⁷¹ The divine epithet *Arm of Yahweh* corresponds to Anat as the warrior consort of Yahweh (*Anat-Yhw*). The veiled nature of the reference may have gotten it past the late editors who purged the texts of heterodoxy (see 1 Chr 8:33-34 vs. 2 Sam 2:10, 4:4 for example). A Neo-Assyrian cylinder seal (Morgan 688, featuring Ištar with her rhomb symbol) appears to depict a Mesopotamian version of this myth and battle scene.

⁷² The biblical sea serpent *Rahab* (רהב) is employed as a metaphor for Babylon as the enslaving entity of the exile (Isa 51:9-11, Psa 87:4, 89:9-10, cf. Jer 51:34). Cuneiform lexicons (A I/2, Nippur Diri) equate *ra'abu* (NB *raḥābu*—wrath) to NIGIN₂ x 30 + NIGIN₂ x 30—which is also NENNI, the standard place-holder for a supplicant in a substitution ritual. For a male, NENNI was read *annanna* (yet is also ¹Nanna = Akk. *Sîn* = ^d30). For a female, it was read *annannītu* (recalling *Ištar Anunītu*). This latent dualistic potential suggests that from a Judaic perspective, the daughter of the moon god served as the answering (Heb. *ʿānāh*) *entu* of heaven who would rescue the nation (and herself) from the entrapment of ^d30 (Jos 2 vs. Isa 51:9). This cuneiform scribal magic may be seen in Joshua’s circling (NIGIN₂) of Jericho (City of ^d30) and Rahab seven times (Sum. *imin/inim*, Akk. *sebettu/sibittu/šabātu*), which was then destroyed by earthquake (*ra-a-bu*).

Thus, the divine guidance in the *entu* narratives may very well have been conceived as the hand of Ištar/Astarte and later Ištar/Anat/Athena.

11. Was There a High Priestess of a Goddess in Ancient Jerusalem?

Although the textual chronology of the entry of the *entu* into the Hebrew scriptures coincides with the Mesopotamian revival this office under Nabonidus, there is may very well be a historical basis for her recurring presence in the nation’s past. The royal genealogies of Judah feature multiple foreign women, each of whom bears the chosen child in her generation. The Judean cultural acceptance of this history would seem to require an indigenous tradition. Given the religious culture of the nation up to that point in time (the Neo-Babylonian and Persian periods), we may reasonably suppose that the literary entry of the *entu* was not controversial because the people traditionally had a goddess and a high priestess.

A trove of cuneiform tablets from Emar on the far western Euphrates reveals the presence of a NIN.DINGIR (~*entu*) priestess.⁷³ She served in a temple dedicated to the storm god ^dIM (assumed to represent Ba’al) and his consort—apparently the local North Syrian goddess Ḫebat.⁷⁴ Curiously, the patron god of Emar was the agricultural god Dagan, which would seemingly have brought the entuship to his temple. Ba’al was the leading male deity of the Canaanite states of the Mediterranean coast, while his counterpart Tarḫunna headed the pantheons of the Hittite states. However, the eclectic pantheon of Emar also included Hittite and Mesopotamian gods. The ritual relationship between Ḫebat and Ba’al suggests that the powers of the storm god were added to Emar’s divine portfolio through their union upon the bed of the *entu*.

In addition to temples housing anthropomorphic statues, Emar had an open-air sanctuary outside the city with standing stones representing deities. During the installation ritual of the *entu*, the standing stone of Ḫebat was anointed with oil by the priestess. All the stones were then anointed with the blood of sacrificial animals. This syncretistic scene offers a late Bronze Age snapshot of the cultural confluence of Canaanite, Mesopotamian and Hittite religions intermixed with the rites of Syrian nomads in the northern Levant. We may assume that a similar scene unfolded in the southern Levant, where the local Canaanite religion intermingled with Egyptian, Mesopotamian and southern nomadic elements.⁷⁵

⁷³ This entuship could be filled by “*the daughter of any son of Emar*” (as opposed to being restricted to the daughters of the king). A new priestess was chosen by lot every seven years (see Fleming, *Baal’s High Priestess* and Michel, *LBA Emar*). It is evident that the traditional Mesopotamian entuship was reshaped as a product of Emar’s location in far western Mesopotamia at a confluence of Syrian, Anatolian and Canaanite cultures.

⁷⁴ Michel describes the temple as a “*double sanctuary*” (*LBA Emar*, pp. 108).

⁷⁵ The installation of the priestess included a rite called the *great kubadu* in which she ceremonially wielded a “*divine weapon*” (Fleming, *Baal’s High Priestess*). This raises the question of whether the name יֹכַבֵּד (*Yw-kbd*)

The editorial superimposition of post-exilic Mosaic observance upon the biblical accounts of pre-exilic Judah makes it difficult to ascertain actual cultic practices.⁷⁰ Did an office comparable to the entuship once exist in Jerusalem? A trail of clues indicates that it is likely. Maachah (c. 900 BC), mother of King Asa, is referred to by the title *g^ēbîrâh* (גבירה). *Gbr* is the root of the Hebrew concepts of *might, power, hero/heroine, warrior, lord/lady* and the verb *to prevail*. Most English translations render *g^ēbîrâh* as *queen* or *queen mother*. However, the anecdote singles out Maachah for her participation in the cult of Asherah (1 Kgs 15:13), suggesting that *g^ēbîrâh* may have been the title of the high priestess.⁷⁶

The cultic connotation of the office is obscured by the narrator’s portrayal of Asherah-worship as an aberration from the true worship of Yahweh. This editorial condemnation belies the scriptural acknowledgments that a goddess (or multiple goddesses) was commonly worshiped by the people throughout the monarchal era—including Asherah, the Asherot, the Ashtarot, Astarte and the Queen of Heaven. As noted in the previous section, the iconography of Athena on the two faces of the temple coin of the high priest Yohanan is an indicator that goddess-worship was not merely an unorthodox “folk religion”, but rather a feature of the national cult in Jerusalem.

If the women (and men) of Judah venerated a female deity on a normal basis, then the specific citation of an association between the *gebîrâh* and Asherah signals that a woman of the royal house played a key role in the cult of the goddess.⁷⁷ Nicholas Wyatt describes the *gebîrâh* of Jerusalem as the “embodiment” of the patron goddess of the city from whom the royal lineage was required to descend (hinted in 2 Chr 11:21-22).⁷⁸ If this reconstruction is correct, then the priestess and the goddess were deeply and intrinsically interconnected with the kingship.⁷⁹

Although goddess-worship is repeatedly condemned as a deviation from the Law of Moses, the historical record shows that it was in fact longstanding normative practice. William Dever cites extensive archaeological traces of veneration of a Canaanite goddess who was viewed as Yahweh’s

given to Moses’ Levite birth mother (Num 26:59) had a meaning derived from her implicit consecration as *entu*, since she plays the part Sargon’s priestess mother.

⁷⁶ The *g^ēbîrâh* Jezebel apparently led the cult of Asherah in the northern kingdom (2 Kgs 10:13). See Ackerman (*Queen Mother*) for discussion of the association of the *g^ēbîrâh* with Asherah.

⁷⁷ Dever (*God Wife*) viewed the goddesses Asherah, Astarte and Anat as a syncretized collective. Nevertheless, they were distinguished by name. The cultural tradition of recognizing a *genius loci* suggests that while the goddesses shared traits, their local expression was specific. It is the critical narrator (the Deuteronomist) who lumps them together and dismisses them as the Asherot or Ashtarot. Given its royal dimension, the office of the *g^ēbîrâh* in Jerusalem was more likely linked to Astarte than to Asherah (see 1 Kgs 11:5, 2 Kgs 23:13).

⁷⁸ Wyatt, *Royal Religion*, p. 75.

⁷⁹ Hebrew *gbr* (גבר) is a cognate of Akk. *gabrû* (*BDB Lexicon*, H1397), meaning *copy* or *equivalent*. The CAD cites the phrase *malku gabrâ ul ibši* (~no king was my equal). In this Semitic language context, the title *gebîrâh* may have identified the high priestess as the *copy* (human representative) of the goddess—which is why the legitimate royal heir had to come from her womb.

divine consort.⁸⁰ They were ritually invoked as a divine couple.⁸¹ Although this idea may appear blasphemous to practitioners of the monotheistic faiths, the appearance of unorthodoxy is an anachronism. The theological conception of single deity did not clearly emerge until much later in history.⁸² An alternative scholarly view holds that the ancient Israelites were *henotheists*—asserting that they believed in the existence of many gods, but only worshiped Yahweh (see Exod 12:12, 15:11, 20:2-3). This classification likewise belies the archaeological record.⁸³

The biblical accounts themselves disclose that neither king nor commoner was familiar with the Mosaic orthodoxy that the post-exilic narrator expected them to observe. The abject ignorance of the pre-monarchal era of the Judges (see Jdg 21:24-25) still prevailed when the lost scroll of the *Torah of Yahweh by the Hand of Moses* was unexpectedly found during the reign of King Josiah near the end of the monarchy (2 Chr 34:14-25, cf. 2 Kgs 22:8-17). When this elusive scroll was rediscovered again by Ezra under Persian rule after the return of the exiles, the people did not even know about Sukkot, the Mosaic fall harvest festival (Neh 8:1-17). The literary birth of Moses during the exile corresponds to the absence of his name in the pre-exilic archaeological record. It explains why the socio-legal system attributed to him was not (and could not have been) followed in antiquity—despite the cameo appearances of his scroll. These often conflicting anecdotes were presumably inserted to support the precedence of later laws codified in Moses' name (e.g. Neh 8:1-17 vs. Ezr 3:2-4, 2 Chr 8:12-13).⁸⁴

Taken as whole, the biblical narrative admits (via criticism and condemnation) that in the period corresponding to 1200-400 BC, the inhabitants of the land generally did not observe the Law of Moses. However, the nation did not exist in a religious vacuum during eight centuries of Mosaic ignorance. It is clear from both archaeology and scriptural accounts that the people actively

⁸⁰ Dever, *God Wife*.

⁸¹ The worship of a divine consort is rejected by Lemaire (*Birth of Monotheism*, pp. 50-51, 57-62), who states that 1st millennium Asherah was not a goddess but merely a symbolic tree in the divine sanctuary. Lemaire posits that the tree must have “*assumed some of the sacred power of YHWH*”. This claim ignores many other biblical attestations of goddess-worship in Israel. In the polytheistic worldview of the biblical era, male gods were matched with female counterparts. Yahweh (who is clearly male) thus required a goddess consort.

⁸² The evolution of monotheistic belief over time is widely recognized by historians, with disagreements over when the critical transformation occurred (see Lemaire, *Birth of Monotheism* and Kirsch, *God Against the Gods*).

⁸³ The appearance of henotheism in the text may be largely an artifact of Hasmonean era credos inserted alongside older material in the final redaction. If all the biblical accounts are viewed as an expression of a single, unitary religious philosophy, the divergent layers merge into a flattened and misleading picture.

⁸⁴ Van Seters (*The Pentateuch*) observed that the legal code attributed to Moses underwent “*many changes and modifications that can be seen from the comparison of laws dealing with the same subject in the different (biblical) sources*” (p. 166). These were finalized when the editors gained “*the necessary authority over the religious community in Jerusalem and thus over the religious texts that governed its life*” (p. 185).

practiced a non-Mosaic religion throughout the biblical era.⁸⁵ Their beliefs and rites did not remain static, but rather evolved during centuries of interaction with other cultures.

From the perspective of tangible history (in contrast to the idealized and retroactive standards of the late editors), the goddess-worship of the nation was not a corruption of the true religion of the ancestors. To the contrary, the role of the goddess was integral to the ancestral way of life.⁸⁶ Archaeological excavations in southern Israel and the Sinai give us a glimpse of the religious observances of the inhabitants of the arid southern fringes of Canaan in antiquity. These nomads venerated a goddess they called Baalat (meaning *Mistress*). She was the patroness of the copper mines that comprised the economic base on this region, along with animal husbandry.⁸⁷

The plan of a temple discovered at the copper mining center of Timna (in the heartland of the wilderness wanderings of the ancestors) features standing stones representing Baalat and other deities (whose names are unknown). During a period of Egyptian control (c. 1280-1145), these traditional *massebot* were worshiped alongside an anthropomorphic statue of the Egyptian goddess Hathor standing in a cella.⁸⁸ The goddess of the coppersmiths was evidently understood to be Hathor's aniconic counterpart.⁸⁹

The ethos of the nomadic coppersmith is attested in the biblical accounts that are set in that time and place (see Exod 35:30-33, 38:1-8, cf. Gen 4:20-22, 47:3).²⁶ They were either the direct ancestors of Judah or closely related by kinship and culture. This relationship is signaled in the representational accounts of Moses' in-laws (Exod 3:1, Num 10:29) and the integration of the Kenites into the tribe Judah (Jdg 1:16, 1 Chr 2:55). Uzi Avner notes overlapping clan names among

⁸⁵ Some Jewish holidays certainly had a pre-Mosaic form—especially Pesach (פסח/פסחא), which does not mean *Passover*. It was celebrated on variable dates in Elephantine before the arrival of “Mosaic” instructions in 419 BC (see Crowley, *Aramaic Papyri*, pp. xxiv-xxvii and Van der Toorn, *Ezra in Egypt*, pp. 603-604).

⁸⁶ Both sexes of deity were worshiped across the Fertile Crescent in antiquity. If the Hebrew creation story is read without the assumption of monotheism, it plainly states that humans were created male and female in the “*image of the elohim*”—the gods (Gen 1:27). This plural and gendered understanding is implicit in the account of the impregnation of human women by “*the sons of the elohim*” (Gen 6:4). If they were male deities and possessed sex organs for copulation, it means that they normally consorted with females of their own kind—*ergo* goddesses.

⁸⁷ The mines also yielded the copper-bearing gems turquoise, azurite and malachite.

⁸⁸ See Avner, *Egyptian Timna*, p. 104-110.

⁸⁹ Evidence at this archaeological site and others suggests that the key cultic contamination of ancient Israel was not polytheism. Instead, the replacement of groups of uncarved (or lightly touched up) standing stones (embodying the gods) erected by nomads with the “graven images” of the city-dwellers egregiously violated a fundamental taboo (see Avner, *Origin of Yhwh*). This taboo was enshrined in the Ten Commandments, yet violated in the designs of Solomon's temple. The purported House of Yahweh in Jerusalem was built by Phoenician craftsmen specializing in “pagan” temple construction. Although the account is largely figurative, it concedes the extensive assimilation of urban Canaanite culture by the settled nomadic tribes in antiquity.

the Israelite, Edomite, Midianite and Amalekite tribes of this region in the biblical genealogies, which suggests that tribal membership among these nomads was fluid over time.⁹⁰

Moreover, the historical trajectories of the smith clans and other nomadic groups of the south were bound together by climate change. The century-long drought of the Late Bronze Age Collapse forced livestock herders to seek refuge where water was available.²⁹ Many closely or loosely related clans converged in the highlands of Canaan (e.g. the *mixed multitude* of Exod 12:38). There they merged with the local sedentary population and eventually formed the kingdoms known from the Bible.²⁹ Although extensive intermarriage is acknowledged in the Hebrew accounts of the settlement of the land, it is described through the lens of cultic corruption (e.g. Jdg 3:5-7). However, the accusation that the Canaanites were responsible for Israel's deviation from the exclusive Yahwism of the nomadic ancestors ignores the reality of the pre-settlement culture and religion of the desert clans.

The temple of Baalat in Timna housed a “*rich hoard*” of votive or ritual objects, including a copper serpent reminiscent of the *Nehushtan* that was venerated in 8th century Jerusalem (II Kgs 18:4).⁸⁸ This ancient icon was reportedly fashioned by Moses from copper to cure snakebite during the era of the ancestral nomadic encampment (Num 21:6-9).⁹¹ Such anecdotes link the old religion of the desert to the temple cult of the settled nomads in Jerusalem. In fact, scores of ancient copper serpents have been discovered in Israel.⁹² These attest to widespread cultic and/or apotropaic use. It is clear that the nomads did not simply adopt Canaanite practices, but rather adapted their ancestral beliefs to a new land that possessed an ancient religious history of its own.

Two biblical towns named *Ba'ālat* (Jos 19:44, 1 Kgs 9:18, 2 Chr 8:6) indicate cultural ties to the goddess.⁹³ Another site, *Ba'ālat Be'ēr* (Jos 19:8), signifies *Mistress of the Well*. A similar place name, *Be'ēr Lahai Rō'î* (*Well of the Being Who-Sees-Me*), is attributed to the appearance of a protective divinity at a water source (Gen 16:6-14). These toponyms indicate that the goddess worshiped by the coppersmiths had locally distinct forms. Each was theistically related to others sharing her name, yet not the exact same entity. After the nomads moved north and settled the highlands, her name receded into history. The traditional cultural position of Baalat was

⁹⁰ Avner (*Origin of Yhwh*, pp. 4-6). Some of these clans are attested in the archaeological record, especially the *Qeni/Qinu/Qainuka* copper smiths. See also 1 Chr 2:54-55 for the founding of Bethlehem and surrounding towns by the *Qinim* (*Kenites* in the KJV).

⁹¹ The sympathetic magic of the *Nehushtan* (*Nḥštn*) derives from the shared Hebrew roots of *copper* (*nḥš*, *nḥšt*), *serpent* (*nḥš*) and *enchantment* (*nḥš*). This semantic field highlights the magical and apotropaic powers inherently wielded by the ancestral *Qinim* (Ecc 10:10-11, Num 23:23, Jdg 4:11-24, 5:24-31).

⁹² The *Nehushtan* pavilion of the Eretz Yisrael Museum (Tel Aviv) houses a large collection of these serpents.

⁹³ See Mullen, *Baalat*. She was also worshiped in Byblos, where she was likewise identified with Hathor. This link to southern Canaan and Egypt attests to the flow of culture and religion in antiquity.

relinquished to the goddesses of southern Canaan. This transition offers us insight into the historical process and cultural dynamics of the nomadic settlement of Canaan.

The prolonged and devastating drought of the Late Bronze Age Collapse forced the nomads to leave the rugged steppe and migrate in search of water sources and living shrubs for their livestock to browse. They left the land in which their ancestors were buried and entered a new territory. As they adapted to the new environment of the central highlands of Canaan, they faced not just the ordinary dangers present in the unfamiliar landscape, but also the threat of hostile and monstrously terrifying ancestral spirits (Deu 1:26-29, 2:10-20, cf. Isa 14:9). The power of local gods was fully understood to be physically real.⁹⁴ The prevailing worldview at that time required the ritual appeasement of the native deities of the foreign land that became their new home—the “*unknown gods, new gods of local origin whom your forefathers feared not*” (Deu 32:17).

The concept of the local hegemony of the *genius loci* is explicit or implicit in multiple biblical accounts. This is clearly laid out in an anecdote concerning the foreigners who were resettled in Samaria by the Neo-Assyrian Empire in place of the deported Israelites (late 7th cent. BC). The narrator explains that the strangers were repeatedly attacked by lions due to their failure to placate the local deity—who in this case was Yahweh (2 Kgs 17:24-41). According to the account, the foreign settlers appealed to the king of Assyria, who repatriated an exiled priest to instruct them in the cult practices of Yahweh. The narrator signals that this mitigation plan was successful despite the foreigners’ continued worship of the gods they brought with them from their own lands, whom they venerated alongside Yahweh.

It is striking that this chronicler presumed that Yahweh—whom the nomads brought with them from the desert—was the legitimate *genius loci* of Samaria. It informs us that by the time story was written, Yahweh had become the recognized deity of the place. How did this happen? What cultic process was required for this indigenization to occur? Yahweh’s transformation is attested archaeologically in the Kuntillet Ajrud inscriptions (c. 800 BC), which invoke *Yahweh of Samaria and his Asherah* and also *Yahweh of Teman and his Asherah*.⁸⁰ It is significant that each local form of Yahweh was attached to a local Asherah. This coupling suggests the answer to the question of how Yahweh of the southern desert became the legitimate god of central Canaan.

The existence of several Amorite states in Canaan prior to the arrival of the tribes of Israel (Exod 33:1-2, Num 21:26) informs us that there was a cultural template for integrating nomadic conquerors into the religious structure of the Canaanites.⁹⁵ If we take the conquest of Mesopotamian city states by Amorite nomads as a model, there was an established naturalization

⁹⁴ For example, the combined forces of Israel, Judah and Edom campaigning in Moab were supernaturally driven from Kir Hareseth by a divine wrath that arose after the Moabite king sacrificed his son (presumably to secure the help of the *genius loci*) upon the wall of the city (2 Kgs 3:21-27).

⁹⁵ For example, the Amorite leader Sihon is credited with subjugating Moab (Num 21:27-29), yet the biblical narratives indicate that the Moabite religion continued without interruption.

procedure. The poem “*Marriage of Martu*” describes the wooing of the daughter of the local patron god by a foreign deity—the patron god of the conquering Amorites.⁹⁶ Their marriage served to integrate this shepherd deity into the local pantheon.⁹⁷

The poem draws upon the ancient pastoralist/sedentary cultural assimilation rites underlying the famed courtship between the deities Dumuzi (Tammuz) and Inanna (Ištar). She rejected the advances of the god of farming and chose the shepherd god instead.⁹⁸ This motif reappears in the account of Cain the farmer and Abel the shepherd, who vie with each other for the favor of Yahweh (Gen 4:1-5). Like Inanna, Yahweh chose the shepherd.⁹⁹ By the mid-1st millennium BC (and beginning much earlier during periods of contact with Mesopotamia), the idea of the ancient courtship of Ištar with its associated rituals had spread across the region.¹⁰⁰ If we interpolate her back into the story of Cain and Abel, it is she who chose the shepherd.

The association between the patron god of the southern nomads and local Canaanite goddesses repeats this pattern. It signals that the successful relocation of Yahweh the Shepherd (Deu 32:9-10, Gen 49:24, Psa 23:1-6) from the desert to Jerusalem required cultic legitimation through “marriage” to the female *genius loci*.¹⁰¹ In the cultural and historical context of the ancient Fertile Crescent, the union between the Judean king and the *gebîrâh* may be understood as the human enactment of this divine event. In keeping with the Mesopotamian rites, we would expect that the *hieros gamos* of Yahweh took place in the temple of the local goddess.

Jerusalem existed for a thousand years before the nomads arriving from the steppe brought Yahweh and his sacred tent (2 Chr 1:4). Like any city of its era, Canaanite Jerusalem certainly had

⁹⁶ See Black, Green and Rickards (*Gods and Demons*, pp. 129-130).

⁹⁷ Beaulieu (*Amurru*) argues that both the marriage and the god Martu were literary creations, although the poem describes a historical cultural accommodation. By the same token, many of the stories told by the Hebrew scribes recreate historical-cultural patterns in representational form. Intriguingly, Martu was sometimes identified with the logogram ^dKUR (*Mountain God*), equivalent to Heb. El Shaddai. The latter is cited as the patriarchal cognomen of Yahweh (see Exod 6:3 and Albright, *Shaddai*, pp. 184-193).

⁹⁸ See ETSCL, *Inana and Dumuzid*.

⁹⁹ Inanna was known by the deity number 15 (cuneiform U.IA₂). Syllables were often reversed in the pronunciation of logograms (e.g. ZU.AB = *Abzu*), making her YAH.U (Heb. *Yhw*). This language link may explain how a Judean scribe in Babylon was inspired to reinterpret the tale by substituting Yahweh for Ištar. Or perhaps it was actually ^d15 who chose the shepherd Abel, with the substitution occurring later.

¹⁰⁰ Dumuzi seems originally to have been a farming god. He later became identified with an allopatric shepherd deity, perhaps due to sharing the same constellation (Agru/Immeru the Ram). Similarly, Inanna merged with the Akkadian warrior goddess Ištar. Thorkild Jacobsen makes a compelling case that in ancient Sumer (before the nomadic conquests), the ritual union of this divine pair symbolized the fertilization of the date palm (*Early Political Development*, p. 108).

¹⁰¹ This explains how *Yahweh of Shomron and his Asherah* could be culturally conceptualized and cultically distinguished from divine couples sharing the same names in other locations.

one or more sanctuaries in which a principal deity and associated divinities were worshiped.¹⁰² The fact that the pre-existing religious practices of Jerusalem are not discussed at all in the Hebrew account of David’s entry into his future capital is a striking absence. However, the Jebusite refusal of entry to the blind and the lame of Judah is narratively linked to the presence of an ancient sacred sanctuary (2 Sam 5:6, cf. Lev 21:8-23).¹⁰³

The Tel Amarna tablets preserve diplomatic correspondence between the Canaanite ruler of Jerusalem and the Egyptian pharaoh Akhen-Aten (r. 1351-1334), more than three centuries before David’s arrival. Unfortunately, the tablets offer little insight into the pre-Judean religious practices of the city. Nevertheless, the cuneiform syllabic spelling of the city’s name in the 14th century BC offers a potential clue. The element “*uru*” in *U₂-ru-ša₁₀-lim* (which can also be read as *U₂-ru-sa-lim*) is the conventional Mesopotamian prefix for “*city*”. Thus, the Akkadian form *Uru-šalim* signifies *City of Šalim*.¹⁰⁴ Although this may be construed as *City of Well-being*, Canaanite place names were often hyphenated with the title of the local deity (e.g. *Beth-Shemesh*, *Beth-Jerah*, *Kiryat-Baal*). Šalim was a Canaanite god. The most coherent cultural reconstruction is that the city was once known as the dwelling place of this deity.

Šalim was identified with the evening star (Venus) in Ugarit during the 2nd millennium BC.¹⁰⁵ However, in Mesopotamia (and eventually across the Fertile Crescent and the Mediterranean), the brightly shining star was perceived as a female astral entity.¹⁰⁶ According to Jeremiah, a goddess called the *Queen of Heaven* (Ištar /Astarte) was zealously venerated before and after the Babylonian conquest (Jer 7:18, 44:17-19)—corresponding to the late 7th to early 6th century BC. Given the local popularity of this goddess and the putative link between the Canaanite city and Venus, her worship in Jeremiah’s time was not a recent introduction (although new cultic practices were certainly added over time).

¹⁰² The account of Melchizedek “*priest to El Elyon*” (Gen 14) has the (intended) effect of preserving the sanctity of Jerusalem by emphasizing the worship of a pre-Judaic high god while avoiding mention of the heterodox cultic history of the place.

¹⁰³ This sense is confounded by an editorial gloss that deliberately changes the plain meaning of “*the blind and the lame shall not come into the temple*” into an insult that inspired the “*smiting*” of the city by Judah (2 Sam 5:6-8). The fact that a Jebusite priest-king held office near the end of David’s reign contradicts or significantly modifies the conquest narrative (2 Sam 24:23).

¹⁰⁴ The lexical list Aa vi/4:1 gives *u₂-ru URU* as Akk. *alu* (*city, village, fort*). The phrase *mâtāt URU u₂-ru-sa-lim^{ki}* (Knudtzon, *El-Amarna*, p. 866) is literally the *land of the city of Salim^{place}*. The short form *Šalem* in the account of Melchizedek (Gen 14:18) suggests that *yeru/uru* was an optional prefix.

¹⁰⁵ Huffman (*Shalem*) notes that Ugaritic Šalim was paired with his twin Šaḥar. They respectively embodied the evening and morning star.

¹⁰⁶ The eight-pointed star symbolizing Venus appears together with the figure of a bare-breasted woman seated on a lion in the art of Elam in the mid 3rd millennium BC (Rogers, *Ancient Constellations*, p. 10). The female imagery of Venus was later adopted by the Greco-Roman civilization and continued to the Renaissance.

If Šalim was once the god of Jerusalem, then the namesake deity of the place was astral in nature. At some point in time, the gender of the patron deity evidently changed.¹⁰⁷ The royal annals of Judah disclose that Solomon king of Israel built a *bāmâh* (open air cultic platform) for Astarte (אשתרת) on the southern shoulder of the Jerusalem ridge (2 Kgs 23:13).¹⁰⁸ Although the historicity of Solomon still awaits archaeological confirmation, the heterodox aspects of his reign are intriguing since their preservation goes against the late editorial grain. Centuries later, Ezekiel (a contemporary of Jeremiah) described the women of Jerusalem weeping for Tammuz the Shepherd (Ezek 8:14)—the divine consort of Ištar. Despite the Mesopotamian flavor of these rites, they clearly resonated within the local West Semitic culture. In all likelihood, these practices were integrated into the ancient cult of Astarte of Jerusalem.

The narrator calls Astarte the “*abomination of the Sidonians*”. Yet Sidonian craftsmen were hired to build the so-called First Temple and the Second Temple (1 Kgs 5:6, Ezr 3:7). If the Sidonians (and Tyrians) were expert temple builders, then their experience came from building “pagan” temples—a fact that did not deter the contemporary Judeans who hired them. Sidon and Tyre were coastal Canaanite city states. Jerusalem was an ancient Canaanite city that became the Judean capital. If Astarte (female Venus) succeeded Šalim (male Venus) as patroness of the city, then the Queen of Heaven was the *genius loci*. This history supplies the missing background for the vehement response of the women of Jerusalem to Jeremiah when the prophet purportedly condemned their worship of the goddess:

But rather we will certainly perform every word of the vows we have made: to burn sacrifices to the Queen of Heaven and to pour out drink offerings to her, just as we ourselves and our forefathers, our kings and our princes did in the cities of Judah and in the streets of Jerusalem; for [then] we had plenty of food and were prosperous and saw no misfortune.

Jer 44:17, AMP

From a Jerusalem-centric viewpoint, Yahweh was originally the foreign god, while Astarte was the native goddess.¹⁰⁹

The begrudging acknowledgement of a *bāmâh* dedicated to Astarte very likely minimizes the importance of the sanctuary as well as the goddess. We should instead expect a full temple devoted

¹⁰⁷ The substitution of deity gender over time is well attested in the ancient Near-East for divinities operating within the same phenomenal area of power (see Black & Green, *Gods and Demons*).

¹⁰⁸ Wyatt (*Astarte*). The name °štrt (*Aštōret*) is cited as the feminine form of °ttr (*Athtar*), both representing deified Venus.

¹⁰⁹ Wyatt (*Astarte*) identifies the goddess of Byblos (*Baalat*) as a “local Astarte”. This suggests that the Judean nomads arriving in Jerusalem in the 10th century BC may have perceived the resident goddess Astarte as a form of their tribal patroness Ba’alat. In the 2nd century AD, Lucian identified the goddess of Byblos as Greek “Aphrodite”—who is Ištar in her manifestation as the goddess of love.

to the divine patroness of Jerusalem.¹⁰³ A free-standing 10th century structure unearthed by Eilat Mazar in the Ophel area between the City of David and the acropolis may be the temple of Astarte. Although not identified as such by Mazar, the layout corresponds to the common pattern of the temples of Ištar/Astarte in antiquity.¹¹⁰ Particularly notable is the round niche carved into the bedrock floor, aligned upon the central NE/SW axis. It may have secured the base of the cultic statue, positioned to face the rising Evening Star.¹¹¹

The cult of Astarte in Sidon featured a high priestess who also served a critical royal function. Two inscriptions inform us that the priest-king Tabnit sired his heir Eshmunazar with the priestess of Astarte.¹⁰⁸ In this respect, she may be considered a Canaanite version of the Mesopotamian *entu*. If a Sidonian-style cult of Astarte was present in 10th century Jerusalem, it stands to reason that a priestess also played a role in the royal succession there. Unfortunately, the modern political conflict over the Temple Mount prevents archaeological excavations of the summit of the Jerusalem ridge. Such digs would help fill significant gaps in our knowledge. This leaves us with the task of reconstructing the nature of worship in Judean Jerusalem by sorting through biblical anecdotes, names and titles, extra-biblical citations and excavations outside the acropolis.

The account of Samuel informs us that a Jebusite king called *Arunah* or *the Arunah* kept the sacred *goren* at the summit of the Jerusalem ridge in the time of David (2 Sam 24:16-23).¹⁷ This is a shocking narrative admission. The revelation that a Canaanite priest-king was present in the latter stages of David's reign points to a critical backstory that is masked in the surviving account.¹¹² How could two kings—one a Canaanite, the other a Judean nomad—coexist in the same city? The relationship between Arunah and David is presented as peaceful by the narrator—yet we never hear of this Jebusite king or his heirs again. The unavoidable conclusion is that the Davidic dynasty replaced its Canaanite predecessor—yet this apparently occurred without killing the former king. How, then, did this transition happen?

The Sidonian cult of Astarte with its high priestess/royal mother offers a tangible historical means by which this process could have occurred. The story of David's theft of Bathsheba (2 Sam 11:1-5, cf. Psa 51:1-18) hints that she may have been the Jebusite *gebîrâh* through whom the Judean nomads gained the throne of Jerusalem.⁷⁸ Although David had many older sons, they did not

¹¹⁰ Mazar (*Fortified Enclosure*) identifies the building as the “the Far House” (2 Sam 15:17). For floor plans of Venus sanctuaries, see Reade (*Ishtar Temple*) and Esteban and Pellin (*Temples of Astarte*). The memory of this temple may also survive as the “house” Solomon built for “Pharaoh's daughter” (1 Kgs 7:8).

¹¹¹ Hundreds of clay figurines depicting a bare-breasted woman on a rounded base have been recovered in excavations of pre-exilic Judean Jerusalem. Although they closely resemble the fertility statuettes found in much of the ancient Near-East, they differ in having pillar-like bases. It suggests the possibility that they were miniatures of the cult statue that stood in this temple (and its successors).

¹¹² He is called *ʾrwnh* and *hʾwrnh* (phps. meant as *ha-ʾarūnâh*) in the same priestly sense that we see in the archetypal name *ʾahârôn* (cf. Arab. *hârûn*, Akk. *bīt harû* sanctuary).

succeed him. It was Bathsheba’s son Solomon who was divinely chosen to become king. It is noteworthy that Bathsheba’s name in this narrative differs from her name in the genealogy of Judah (1 Chr 2:3/3:5). There she is *Bathshua*—who is identified as *the Canaanitess* in the ancestral prequel.¹¹³ The altered element *šeba* means *oath*.⁶² It suggests that the *Daughter of the Oath* was required to establish David’s Judean dynasty.¹¹⁴

David and his band of warrior nomads were newcomers to Jerusalem. If Bathsheba was a “Jebusite”, then she was both native to the place and foreign to the Judean nomads who entered Jerusalem and assimilated its rites.¹¹⁵ By conceiving Solomon with her, David laid a legitimate claim upon the rulership of ancient Jerusalem.¹¹⁶ As the human representative of Yahweh, David’s union with the priestess of Astarte concomitantly established the tribal god of Judah upon his new throne in Jerusalem.

12. Conclusion

The account of Solomon’s marriage to the daughter of an unnamed Pharaoh (1 Kgs 3:1) has the ring of another iteration of the *entu* of Ur/Harran. She plays the female lead in the Song of Songs.¹¹⁷ Solomon (Sng 1:8-9) likens her to “*my mare*” (*sūsati*) among the “*chariots of Pharaoh*” (*rikbei-par’ōh*). Akkadian *šūšūtu* designates a wife who leaves. The metaphor may be understood as a sexual pun with a dynastic twist.¹¹⁸ Hebrew *rākab* is a cognate of Akkadian *rakābu*—*to mount*,

¹¹³ The first wife of Judah (the ancestral personification of the future tribe) was “*Bathshua the Canaanitess*”. She was replaced as mother of the royal dynasty by the *entu* Tamar, suggesting a symbolic interplay with Bathsheba, who likewise “replaced” Bathshua (her former self). The two citations of *Bathshua* occur in the same retrospective genealogical construct, signaling cryptic linkage between the parallel names.

¹¹⁴ This concept may reappear in the Book of Revelation, which identifies Jesus as both the divine root and human offspring “*of David and the bright morning star*” (Rev 22:16, depunctuated NIV; cf. Peshitta).

¹¹⁵ The ancestry attributed to Bathsheba only goes as far back as her grandfather Ahithophel (2 Sam 11:3, 23:34), whose forebears are not listed in the genealogies of the tribes. The text hints that he was a priest who served “as oracle of the gods” (2 Sam 16:23-17:2).

¹¹⁶ The story of Bathsheba/Uriah (*Daughter of the Oath/Light of Yahweh*) is patently allegorical, as are the linked accounts of Absalom/Ahithophel and the civil wars of the latter stages of David’s reign. Even so, the exilic-era composition is mapped onto Judean history, preserving some aspects of it.

¹¹⁷ See Sasson (*Dark Lady*). However, a trend in recent scholarship contests this longstanding identification. The confusion may be attributed in part to the representational nature of the *entu*. Her identity as Pharaoh’s daughter is only one of her guises. In the same poem she is also Ištar, calling to the shepherd Tammuz (1: 7).

¹¹⁸ The mare (מָרָה/מָרָה) is a *hapax legomenon* whose exclusive appearance in a figure of speech signals a cryptic Akkadianism. The mare initially belonged to *par’ōh*, suggesting a derogatory pun on *parū* (*mule*)—evoking sterility and the end his dynasty. In the context of the entuship of Ur (אור), *sūsati* evokes *šāšūtu* as the

mate, fertilize. It is written with the logogram U₅—which also represents *kiššatu* (*all, totality, world*). The metaphor identifies her as the dynastic matrix of the royal harem who chooses Solomon as her lover, making him the *šarru kiššati*.

This *hieros gamos* is echoed in Psalm 45 (*Shir Yedidot—Song of Lovers*), where the royal bride is the daughter of the king of Tyre. Once again, we see that her characteristic foreign origin is geographically fungible, underscoring the figurative nature of the *entu* in the biblical narrative. As the princess of Tyre, she is culturally linked to the royal priestesshood that is historically attested in the cult of Astarte in neighboring Sidon.¹⁰⁸ It triangulates with Solomon’s construction of a sanctuary for the practice of the “Sidonian” cult of Astarte in Jerusalem. The complexity deepens with the allegorical substitution of the King of Tyre for the King of Babylon (see Eze 28:12-17 vs. Isa 14:4, 12-16). In both prophecies, the human king is the embodiment of a powerful celestial being. By extension, the daughter of the King of Tyre is both priestess and goddess.

It has long been noted that the Song of Songs is a duet in the tradition of the Mesopotamian marriage ritual of Tammuz and Ištar.¹¹⁹ The princess identifies herself to the daughters of Jerusalem as an exotically beautiful foreigner, whom they then adorn with gold and silver and a sachet of perfume like priestesses attending a cult statue (Sng 1:5-13). She is called a “dove” (the dualistic symbol of Astarte) and the “chosen one” of her goddess mother (Sng 6:9).¹²⁰ The divine aspect of her identity is revealed through the poetic device of a question that unveils the astral goddess of love and war:

Who is she that looketh forth as the morning,
Fair as the moon, clear as the sun,
And terrible as an army with banners? Sng 6:10, KJV

The princess calls to the king, saying “*I will bring you to the house of my mother who taught me*” (Song 8:2). Clearly, she is not referring to her childhood home in “Egypt”. As high priestess, she speaks of the temple of her goddess in which *the hieros gamos* will take place.

The Song of Songs may be understood as the culmination of the foundational entuship envisaged by the Judean scribes of the exile. In it, the Hebreo-Akkadian *entu* princess-priestess becomes the wife of the rustic shepherd king after ritual disseveration from her emperor father. The

lantern of the City of Light (ŠEŠ^{ki}) and the daughter-wife of Sîn (ŠEŠ^{ki}). It may also play upon *šašû / sasiu* (*to call / be invited*) and *šūšûtu* (as the *announcement* of her transfer of allegiance).

¹¹⁹ Kramer (*Sumerian Love Songs*) identifies the core of the poem as liturgy of the Mesopotamian *hieros gamos* that was adopted by the cult of Astarte.

¹²⁰ The dove iconography of Ištar/Astarte is well attested (see Keel and Uehlinger, *Gods and Images*). Akk. *uršānu* (fem. *uršānatu*) means both *dove* and *warrior hero*. The Heb. phrase יֹנָתִי (*yônâti—my dove*) is equivalent to Akk. *uršānat-ya*, recalling *ûršanât-ilī* (*warrior goddess—a title of Ištar*). *Uršānu* is written with the logogram KASKAL.SAG, which may be read as *Slave of Harran, Gift of Harran* and *Foremost of Harran*.

consummation of their union reciprocally removes the high honor and vast wealth of the *šarru kiššati* (*King of All the Lands*) and bestows it upon the chosen nation.

In the *Shir Yedidot*, the divinely ordained future of the foreign royal bride who marries the king is laid out by the psalmist:

Hearken, O daughter ... and incline thy ear,
 Forget also thine own people and thy father's house ...
 Instead of thy father(s) shall be thy children,
 Whom thou mayest make princes in all the earth,
 I will make thy name to be remembered in all generations:
 Therefore shall the people praise thee for ever and ever. Ps 45:10, 16-17, KJV

We never hear of Pharaoh's daughter again. Instead, her identity merges with Jerusalem as the embodiment of Astarte, the patroness of the ancient city.¹²¹ Her foreign origin is reciprocally exchanged with the persona of the native goddess—the exotic, exquisitely beautiful and incomparably desirable *entu* of the gods. This signals that the poetic epithet *Daughter of Jerusalem* originally referred to Astarte as the *genius loci*. In biblical prophecy, she eagerly awaits the grand arrival of the handsome shepherd king. Their future union will usher in the kingdom of all the earth:

Rejoice greatly, O Daughter of Zion,
 Shout, O Daughter of Jerusalem:
 Behold, thy King cometh unto thee ...
 And his dominion shall be from sea even to sea,
 And from the river even to the ends of the earth.¹²²
 Zech 9:9, KJV

And thou, O Tower of the flock,
 The strong hold of the Daughter of Zion,
 Unto thee shall it come, even the first dominion;
 The kingdom shall come to the Daughter of Jerusalem.
 Mic 4:8, KJV

¹²¹ Note the wordplay between *kalâtô* (כלתו) as both Solomon's bride and the completion of his building of Jerusalem (1 Kgs 3:1).

¹²² This description corresponds directly to the Akk. concept of the *šarrut kiššatim*—the *kingship of all the lands* (LUGAL-ut *kiššati*, NAM.LUGAL KIŠ-ti).

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